

**Canterbury Christ Church University
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Dr Ernesto Hernandez, PhD, CEng, FHEA, MChemE,
MRSC, SMAIChE
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CDIO group report

Sustainable Biodiesel Production from Waste Cooking Oil

Supervisor: Dr Ernesto Hernandez

Authors:

Gurung Misa
Lawson Harry
Pellegrino Tommaso
Wyatt Jack

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Physiochemical properties

Table 1.0.1: Physiochemical properties.

COMPONENT	CHEMICAL FORMULA	RELATIVE FORMULA MASS (KG/KMOL)	HF (KJ/KMOL)	HV (KJ/KMOL)	CP (LIQUID STATE)(KJ/KMOL.K)
BIODIESEL	Varying FAME	≈292 to 310	≈-600	≈42 to 55	≈2.2 to 2.5
CALCIUM SULFOXIDE CAO	Ca ₂ SO ₄ CaO	56.077			
GLYCEROL	C ₃ H ₈ O ₃	92.00	-669.30	≈-60.00	2.43
METHANOL	CH ₃ OH	32.05	-239.10	35.6	79.9
SULFURIC ACID	H ₂ SO ₄	98.08	-814.00	N/A (Thermal decomposition)	1.38
TRIPALMITIN (TG SUBSTITUTE)	C ₅₉ H ₉₈ O ₆	807.339	-2468.7	N/A	1753.1
WATER	H ₂ O	18.02	-285.83	40.65	4.18
WCO	Long chain triglycerides	≈875.00	≈-150 to -200	≈35-50	≈2-2.3

Nomenclature

Table 2.1: Nomenclature.

TERM	DEFINITION
BD100	Pure Biodiesel
BDX	Coding for biodiesel blends where x is the percent volume of biodiesel
BFD	Block flow diagram
BIODIESEL	The American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) defines biodiesel as monoalkyl esters of long chain fatty acids derived from a renewable lipid feedstock, such as vegetable oil or animal fat.
BROWN GREASE	FFA > 20 wt%
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CRO	Crude Rapeseed Oil
CSTR	Continuously stirred tank reactor
DAG	Diacylglycerol
DG	Diglyceride
FAME	Fatty Acid Methyl Ester
FER	Fossil Energy Ratio
FFA	Free Fatty Acid
H₂SO₄	Sulphuric acid
ICE	Internal combustion engine
IV	Iodine value
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
MAG	Monoacylglycerol
MG	Monoglyceride
NAOH	Sodium hydroxide
P&ID	Piping and instrumentation diagram
PFD	Process flow diagram
TAG	Triacylglycerol
TG	Triglyceride
UCO	Used Cooking Oil
VOC	Volatile Organic Compound
WCO	Waste Cooking Oil
YELLOW GREASE	Variant of waste cooking oil, Free fatty acids < 20 wt%

Table 2.2: Equation symbol, description and associated unit

SYMBOL	DESCRIPTION	UNITS
ΔE_K	Change in Kinetic Energy	kJ hr^{-1}
ΔE_P	Change in Potential Energy	kJ hr^{-1}
ΔH	Change in Enthalpy	kJ hr^{-1}
ΔT	Change in Temperature	K
C_P	Specific Heat Capacity	$\text{kJ kmol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
H_F	Enthalpy of Formation	kJ kmol^{-1}
H_V	Enthalpy of Vaporisation	kJ kmol^{-1}
M	Mass Flow Rate	kg hr^{-1}
$M.R.$	Molecular Mass	kg kmol^{-1}
N	Molar Flow Rate	kmol hr^{-1}
Q	Energy	kJ hr^{-1}
R	Reflux Ratio	Dimensionless
R_{MIN}	Minimum Reflux Ratio	Dimensionless
V_M	Vapor Flow into Condenser	kmol hr^{-1}
V_N	Vapor Flow from Reboiler	kmol hr^{-1}
W	Work	kJ hr^{-1}
X_i	Mol Fraction	Dimensionless

List of contributors

Chapter	Contributors
1	All members contributed to a certain degree
2	All members contributed to a certain degree
3	All members contributed to a certain degree
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10	All members contributed to a certain degree

Chapter 1. Extended summary

Executive summary

This project outlines a sustainable production method for biodiesel with waste cooking oil as a feedstock. This plant met the design initiatives and is able to produce biodiesel which complies to EN 14214 standards at a rate of 600,000 tonnes annually. The acid-catalysed transesterification process was chosen for its ability to handle the fluctuating chemical composition of waste cooking oil which eliminates costly pretreatment steps. The main units include, transesterification reactor, neutralisation reactor, methanol recovery column, glycerol purification column, and biodiesel purification column.

Energy recovery methods such as grand composite curves and heat exchanger networks lower utility costs and reduce the carbon footprint of the plant. Various safety risks arise in the plant from handling hazardous materials such as methanol (flammable), and sulfuric acid (corrosive). Therefore, HAZOP studies, bow tie diagram, and alarm systems integrated to the control loops are outlined in this project. The environmental aspect was also considered throughout the design, a methanol recovery unit improves plant economics and reduces volatile emissions, byproducts such as glycerol will also be valorised instead of wasted. Economically, the plant will require \$282 million in capital expenditure, the second year operational cost is approximately \$950 million, for the first year, and then or \$748 million each year thereafter. The payback is one year, which is enabled only by the government subsidies of renewable fuel.

The plant will be located at Southhampton Science park as it offers logistical advantages being close to ports. The main challenges with the plant involve the scalability as feedstock security becomes a challenge. A consideration of implementing on site storage was done however, the challenges of storage stability of waste cooking oil is grave. Overall this project outlines a plant design in its entirety from conception to implementation.

Appraisal of group design

This project was approached with a strong teamwork, technical diligence, and shared commitment. From the early planning stages to the final report compilation, tasks were efficiently distributed based on individual strengths and interests, which helped us manage the workload and ensure that all sections, the process design, safety assessments, sustainability analysis, and economic evaluation were completed to a high standard. The complexity of producing biodiesel via acid-catalysed transesterification using waste cooking oil posed many challenges, but it also served as an opportunity for learning and innovation.

Among the aspects that worked particularly well was the design of the process diagrams—specifically the Process Flow Diagram (PFD), Block Flow Diagram (BFD), and Piping and Instrumentation Diagram (P&ID). These were developed to a high standard of clarity and detail, integrating iterative feedback and aligning closely with industry norms. Particular attention was paid to the mass and energy balance, which laid the foundation for equipment design such as the size and quantities required and the utilities cost estimation. In line with best practice, energy recovery strategies such as heat exchanger networks were incorporated to improve process efficiency and reduce operational costs.

Another major focus was producing a thorough HAZOP study and Bow-Tie analysis, reflecting an in-depth understanding of process safety and risk management. These safety components were enhanced by the inclusion of a structured Safety Instrumented System (SIS) logic and a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for a critical unit operation, helping to bridge theory and practice.

However, challenges did arise in terms of reaction modelling, and design of reactors and separation equipment. These required deeper research and extensive consultation of literature and industrial case studies. Despite these obstacles, the team remained proactive and communicative. Regular meetings, issuing a progress tracker, and a clear documentation in shared drive were done to deliver a complete and high-quality report.

Some initial difficulties also emerged in aligning the individual design sections into a cohesive and consistent report, especially where unit operation assumptions varied. At times, more guidance would have helped clarify expectations, but we managed to overcome most issues through additional research and group discussion.

This project was executed by a team of final-year chemical engineering students, each bringing different set of skills and a collaborative mindset. Despite the shared academic background, diverse thinking and open dialogue allowed for a range of solutions and strategies to be explored and mitigate challenges. While there is always room for improvement, especially in integrating the report sections more smoothly, our willingness to learn and improve helped us create a strong final design.

In reflection, the group has gained a strong appreciation for the interdisciplinary and iterative nature of the chemical process design. With further experience, the team would be well-positioned to deliver even more refined and industry-ready projects in future scenarios.

Personal appraisal

I was responsible for writing the executive summary, ensuring the project scope and findings are presented. I researched and authored Chapter 3.1 (Production overview) and 3.2 (Applications and uses), finding different review studies and studying different markets for the product around the world both in the past, present and projections for the future. Additionally, in Chapter 3.10 (evaluation process selection), I reviewed multiple production pathways and led the decision making which was to choose the most suitable process based on various factors. I also created the P&ID and plant layout, by mapping out the plant while conforming to health and safety standards, labelling streams, and designed the control systems involved. The final biodiesel purification unit was also designed by me in Chapter 6.4 (major equipment T-401) outlining the main specification sheets. I also wrote the conclusion condensing the whole project into a concise form. Finally, in my role as editor and team leader I arranged all meetings and established all methods of communication and file sharing, and improved and aided my team members in all sections where they fell short to deliver.

My key strengths and improvement I observed throughout this project was enhancement in technical writing skills, to condense the vast data involved into a concise format. My role in market survey and process overview improved my researching skills, enabling me to find up to date and reliable sources to form a foundation of our project. My skills in designing the control system improved quickly as I combined my knowledge from various modules to tackle the task.

I also faced numerous challenges, struggling to balance detail and conciseness in the executive summary and conclusion section needed many iterations while taking on feedback from my team members. Many iterations of the P&ID were required and I struggled at first. However Dr Hernandez aided me in designing the P&ID and vastly improved my proficiency in process flow convention and instrumentation diagram standards which is a vital skill in industry.

I actively assigned peer reviews within the group, adapted suggestions from team members, and arranged meetings in the group and extra sessions with Dr Hernandez. This improved my communication, planning, and collaborative skills. However, I found estimation on how much time a section took to create as a team a challenge, often overshooting the specified timeframe.

To reflect on my design, my major equipment met all the performance requirements which were also proven in an ASPEN simulation. My evaluation of the process pathway chosen and other potential pathways highlighted clearly which is most suited to the process. Main difficulties lied in the presentation of calculation and simulation results in a format which conforms to industry standards.

Overall, this project and the guidance of Dr Hernandez improved me on various vital skillsets valued in industry from technical drawings and presentations, to collaborative skills.

Personal reflection

In the conceive stage of this capstone project, I focused my efforts on finding a fitting study in the literature which would guide us on this project and align with the outlined requirements, such as sustainability and health and safety. I began by researching different feedstocks and which would be most sustainable while providing adequate economic feasibility. Through brainstorming with my team members, I created multiple pathway maps to clearly outline each pathway and feedstock advantages. I learnt the importance of mitigating scope creep, how to balance economic limitation and environmental sustainability, and techniques in concept evaluation such as Pugh matrices.

In the design stage I oversaw the creation of the vital technical illustrations for the process (BFD, PFD, and P&ID). I also created the control system which ensure stable and safe plant operation. I learnt to create standard compliant engineering drawings, the iterative nature of the drawings with various revision stages, and the collaboration skills needed to create an extensive P&ID.

In the implement stage I oversaw the application of the drawings and design calculations into an ASPEN simulation. Ensuring the simulation provided results that deliver performance demanded by the process in the purification stage. I learnt how to condense vast numerical results from hand calculation into a format that a software is able to process. I also learnt how to interpret the simulation outputs and how to utilise them.

Being a student, I did not run any pilot plants but I outlined simulation and hand calculation results in to specification sheets which would usually be sent to a manufacturer to obtain the correct parts for installation in the plant.

Overall, the CDIO objective has been achieved with the guidance from Dr Hernandez, which aided me immensely.

Chapter 2. Design basis

Process scope and objectives

This project aims to consolidate ideas, data and design specifications from the assessment 1 and 3 reports, forming an enhanced design basis that may be used to extract greater insight into plant design and function. The primary objective of the project is to design a biodiesel production plant with an annual production capacity of 600,000 tonnes of fatty acid methyl esters (FAME), conforming to EN 14214 standards for biodiesel production quality. The secondary objective of the project is to do so in a manner that reflects current attitudes towards sustainability within process engineering and within evolving regulatory frameworks. While this complicates the project marginally, brief requirements specify the necessity of considering the entire process lifecycle, as well as environmental and sustainability analyses, thus justifying the importance of the secondary objective. Further, this objective can be attained with some success simply by the chosen process route utilising a waste product as a feedstock. The plant is designed to be as safe as reasonably practicable and to limit environmental impact. One of the major objectives is the incorporation of various energy conservation strategies, including careful process unit design and application of PINCH technology. Just as energy efficiency remains a top priority, so does conformity to various safety standards including ATEX directive 114, HSG regulation 176 and COMAH 2015 regulation 483. Aligning the process design with these regulations enhances operational safety and ensures regulatory compliance. To this end, the report aims to produce detailed safety analyses including bow-tie diagrams and a HAZOP study.

Design basis

The design basis of this report is an expanded continuation of the process framework outlined within the assessment 1 and assessment 3 reports. Waste cooking oil (WCO) was originally selected as a feedstock, and acid-catalysed transesterification was selected as the route of production due to its ability to cope with the variable free fatty acid content of WCO. In the interest of maintaining consistency across reports, as well as using the engineering principle of iterating upon design, the originally selected process has been deemed adequate for the project goals. Additionally, the selection aligns with the objective of delivering a more sustainable production process. The overall design is fundamentally based on four major units: the transesterification reactor, the neutralization reactor for quenching residual acid catalyst and the distillation columns for the main FAME product stream as well as the secondary glycerol byproduct stream for the purposes of both purification as well as methanol recovery. These four units form the basis of the report and outline the major process features that are considered and are outlined within chapter 4 and 6. The production plant is designed to be continuous to ensure capability of reaching the production target, with an uptime of 334 days per year to account for maintenance, troubleshooting or any other process interruptions.

The purified FAME product should meet the requirements laid out by EN 14214 such that the final biodiesel content achieves a minimum ester fraction of 96.5% by weight, a kinematic viscosity between $3.5\text{mm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ and $5.0\text{mm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ at 40°C , as well as an acid value no higher than 0.5mg KOHg^{-1} , and a water content not exceeding 500mgkg^{-1} . This ensures compatibility with diesel fuel systems and allows for the use of the biodiesel product as a fuel additive.

To achieve favourable conversion rates in the transesterification reaction, a molar ratio of 50:1 methanol to oil is used and an amount of 3% sulphuric acid by weight is used (Zhang, 2003). For the neutralisation step, a calcium oxide excess of 10% is used.

Design assumptions and constraints

The chosen process route for the goal of producing 600,000 tonnes of biodiesel (FAME) is acid catalysed transesterification using a pre-treated WCO feedstock. This process will be large-scale and continuous to satisfy the yearly target. For the purposes of this report, it is assumed that WCO is composed of FFAs and TG, as other glycerides are only present in trace quantities (Amirthavalli Velmurugan, 2022, Guanhao Liu, 2020). The reagent quantities were determined via reverse-stoichiometry from the desired product quantity in addition to a mass balance, in combination with the compositions and yields highlighted in the Chemistry(ies) section. (Y Zhang, 2003), the scale factor was 75 and it was assumed that the plant would have a 334 day per year uptime, to account for maintenance needs.

A large excess of methanol is used in the main reaction step to ensure complete reaction and shorter residence time, but the process achieves a high recovery rate due to the inclusion of a coarse distillation step after the transesterification, as well as two further distillation steps to purify the product and biproduct, as depicted in the process diagrams within chapter 4. Following the main esterification reaction a recovery rate of 94% was assumed based on findings in literature. This methanol recovery is environmentally efficient, reducing the need for waste processing and preventing large discharge of methanol in a local area. Operating conditions were set at 80 degrees Celsius and 400 kPa, consistent with findings in the study used as a basis for the scaling. Catalyst impurities in the product streams are dealt with by neutralisation, a water wash and finally a distillation step for the FAME and glycerol streams.

This basis assumes a steady supply of partially pre-treated WCO, as well as ensuring a steady supply of reagents to meet the output goals.

Chapter 3. Process background

3.1 Production overview

Usage of WCO for biodiesel production is characterised by several main stages to transform the economical, readily available, and renewable feedstock into a high-quality fuel. The first step in this process is the pretreatment of the WCO, as the inherent impurity and high levels of FFAs interfere with the process. FFA levels are reduced by acid catalysed esterification, where FFAs are converted into esters, lowering acidity, thereby preparing the feed for the main transesterification reaction (Javidialesaadi and Raeissi, 2013).

After pre-treatment, the transesterification begins; this is the key reaction for producing biodiesel. Triglycerides in the WCO react with methanol in the presence of an alkali catalyst, sodium hydroxide. This produces FAME, a group of chemicals that constitute biodiesel, as well as glycerol in a side reaction. The FAME stream then undergoes further purification to meet fuel quality standards for sale (Kouzu and Hidaka, 2012).

Factors such as reaction temperature, molar ratio and catalyst concentration impact the product quality and yield. This is due to the sensitivity to operating conditions in the transesterification step. Strict operating conditions are essential to maximise biodiesel yield and lower the likelihood of undesired phenomena such as saponification, which can deteriorate the catalyst thus complicating product purification (Sai et al., 2024).

3.2 Application and Uses

Biodiesel is chemically similar to petroleum-based diesel; therefore, it can be a direct substitute for internal combustion uses in place of petroleum diesel (Huang, Zhou and Lin, 2012). However, it is sold as part of a petroleum blend, ranging from 5-7% by mass. The European Union have legislation that permits a maximum concentration of 7% (European Biodiesel Board, 2023). This is due to issues regarding the effects on the fuel system in engines, stability during storage as biodiesel is more prone to mould and bacterial growth. Additionally, its lower calorific value being 37.27 MJ/kg, 9% lower than petroleum diesel means any internal combustion engine (ICE) would need a larger amount of fuel if substituted with biodiesel (Elsayed, 2003). Biodiesel emits less greenhouse gases and pollutants like sulphur oxides, nitrous oxides and particulate matter (Setiyo, Yuvenda and Samuel, 2021).

Biodiesel also has numerous applications in many other industries. For example, it replaces aniline, a toxic chemical used in power generation, agricultural machinery, and marine engines. Biodiesel is also used as heating fuel in heating systems, substituting petroleum-based fuels with biodiesel offers regions aiming to lower their carbon footprint an alternative option to replacing their heating system (Gerhard Knothe, Jurgen Krahl and Harlan, 2010). The lifespan of asphalt surfaces can be extended using bio-based materials. Studies show that biodiesel can effectively restore the rheological properties of asphalt (Zaid Hazim Al-Saffar et al., 2024).

In areas where contamination of the fuel is a concern, such as farming, areas close to the sea, or areas with strict environmental regulations, the biodegradable nature of biodiesel offers an alternative to conventional options (Bayraktar et al., 2023).

3.3 Market survey

The global biodiesel market has experienced substantial growth over the past 3 years with market forecasts showing strong growth patterns. The biodiesel market was valued at approximately \$32.09 billion in 2021 and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 10% until 2030, reaching a value of \$75.67 billion (GVR, 2024). The growth can be attributed to the transition towards a more sustainable future, as fossil-based fuels are being phased out. Government policies and goals to achieve net zero in the future almost guarantee the growth this industry will continue to experience.

The European Biodiesel Board published a statistical analysis which outlined 52 million tonnes of biodiesel were produced globally in 2022, the European Union accounting for approximately 25% at 13.7 million tonnes (EBB, 2023).

The United States, Brazil, and Indonesia are leaders in biodiesel production, accounting for almost 60%. This is a 25% increase compared to 10 years earlier. Countries such as Brazil and India are implementing biodiesel to reduce dependence on fossil fuels as they are net importers of oil, this reduces their dependency. In Brazil, for example, the government biofuel blending mandate plans to increase the share of biodiesel in diesel mixtures to 15% by 2026 (Biofuels International, 2024).

3.4 Physical and Chemical Properties

Biodiesel is a liquid that has a light to dark yellow colour which depends on the type of feedstock used in the manufacturing stages which affects final product composition. The fatty acid methyl and ethyl esters in the composition of biodiesel are constituted of carbon, hydrogen and oxygen atoms that form linear chain molecules with single and double carbon-carbon bonds (Zahira Yaakob, 2013). Table 3.1 presents the physical and the chemical properties of biodiesel that is produced from waste cooking oil.

Table 3.1: Physical and chemical properties of Biodiesel.

Properties	Values	Units
Molecular formula	CH ₃ (CH ₂) _n COOCH ₃	N/A
Molecular weight	284-295	g/mol
Density	897	kg m ³
Kinematic viscosity	5.3	mm ² s ⁻¹
Sulphur content (WT%)	0.006	%
Flash point	469	K
Pour point	262	K
Cetane number	54	N/A
Free Fatty Acid	0.10 mg KOH/g-1	KOH/g-1

3.5 Chemistry(ies)

Biodiesel is composed of fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) that can be prepared by a catalysed transesterification reaction where triglycerides in vegetable oils or animal fats react with an alcohol to yield FAME compounds, along with glycerol as a by-product. The catalyst used can be an alkali, acid or enzyme to accelerate the conversion. The process is similar to hydrolysis, except alcohol is used to displace water to form a new ester instead of water (L.C. Meher, 2004).

Composition of WCO

When discussing the chemistry of the process, it is also necessary to discuss the composition of the WCO, which tends to vary wildly depending on the source. It is comprised mostly of TGs and FFAs, with smaller quantities of DGs and MGs present (R. Abd Rabu, 2013) as well as up to 20% by volume of solid particulate (Juliana Cárdenas, 2021). Table 3.2, obtained from the literature, outlines the percentage composition of a sample of used cooking oil, which is used as a basis for our calculations.

Table 3.2: WCO composition per 100g of oil (Yanyong Liu, 2012).

Elemental composition	C	H	N	S	O
Weight percent (wt%)	77.91	11.69	0.04	0	10.36
Chemical composition	Triglyceride	Diglyceride	Monoglycerid	Free fatty acid	
Content (g/100 g-oil)	79.1	1.8	2.2	16.9	

The FFA value and the TG value are of note due to their involvement in key process reactions; for the purposes of this report, the DG and MG values were added to the TG value due to their trace presence. For the acid esterification reaction, the specific FFA composition must also be known in addition to the total percentage of FFAs in the oil. Table 3.3, also obtained from the literature (Monika et al., 2023), outlines the percentage FFA compositions of three different samples of WCO.

Table 3.3: WCO fatty acid composition (Monika et al., 2023).

Type of Free Fatty Acid	Carbon Chain	Sample A(wt%)	Sample B(wt%)	Sample C(wt%)
Myristic Acid	C14:0	0.99	0.9	0.77
Palmitic Acid	C16:0	28.65	20.4	31.88
Palmitoleic Acid	C16:1	0.97	4.6	-
Stearic Acid	C18:0	2.55	4.8	6.45
Oleic Acid	C18:1	24.69	52.9	41.04
Linoleic Acid	C18:2	40.88	13.5	17.98
Linolenic Acid	C18:3	1.27	0.8	0.43
Others	-	-	1.1	1.45

Acidic esterification step

The acid esterification step is necessary to convert all of the FFA-rich oil. As shown in Figure 3.1, this step involves the reaction of FFAs and TGs in the WCO with methanol in the presence of an acid catalyst, in our case H_2SO_4 . The resulting product is FAME. The literature states that this is a first order rate reaction with a rate constant of 0.0031min^{-1} (Siddharth Jain, 2011). Research by Siddharth et al also indicates that a residence time of 180 mins at 65°C with a molar ratio of 3:7 methanol to oil and an acid

Figure 3.1: Esterification of FFA (Prachasanti Thaiyasuit, 2012).

catalyst content of 1% by weight produces optimal reaction conditions, with an FFA conversion to under 1% and a methyl ester yield of 21.5%.

The specific equations relevant to the WCO of the composition assumed in the previous subsection are as follows and are all in the presence of a H_2SO_4 catalyst.

1. $C_{15}H_{31}COOH + CH_3OH \rightarrow C_{15}H_{31}COOCH_3 + H_2O$
2. $C_{17}H_{35}COOH + CH_3OH \rightarrow C_{17}H_{35}COOCH_3 + H_2O$
3. $C_{17}H_{33}COOH + CH_3OH \rightarrow C_{17}H_{33}COOCH_3 + H_2O$
4. $C_{17}H_{31}COOH + CH_3OH \rightarrow C_{17}H_{31}COOCH_3 + H_2O$
5. $C_{17}H_{29}COOH + CH_3OH \rightarrow C_{17}H_{29}COOCH_3 + H_2O$

Neutralisation step

After the acidic transesterification, the resulting FAME mixture is acidic and unsuitable for downstream processing. Thus, a neutralisation step becomes imperative. A thorough understanding of this step is required for adequate process design.

The neutralisation reaction is the reaction of sulphuric acid catalyst with calcium oxide, to produce water and calcium sulphate, which exists as a precipitate in solution, and the reaction is as follows:

Due to the need to reduce acid content as much as possible, high conversion rates need to be achieved. Fortunately, within industry it is possible to achieve conversion rates as high as 99% by using a 10–15% excess of neutralisation reagent, by stoichiometric ratio [REFERENCE]. To achieve such a conversion with a slurry-phase neutralisation, it is also important to ensure efficient mass transfer and contacting, necessitating the use of an agitator. The optimal reaction conditions for this step are 60°C , 2bar as determined by Zhang et al.

Since both the calcium oxide and calcium sulphate exist as precipitate, downstream processing is simple and may be achieved in one step via a solid-liquid separation unit, making the use of excess inconsequential to separation.

3.6 Review of Alternative Processes (initial process routes)

Transesterification using acid catalyst such as sulfuric acid is commonly used to produce biodiesel, and it is also the focus in this study. However, there are alternative processes that can be considered for biodiesel production varying on the feedstock, type of catalyst, and operating conditions. Some processes are Alkali-Catalysed transesterification, Enzyme-Catalysed transesterification and Supercritical transesterification.

3.6.1 Basic transesterification

For an alkali-catalysed transesterification, the first step involves the attack of the alkoxide ion on the carbonyl carbon of the triglyceride molecule, which results in the formation of a tetrahedral intermediate. The reaction of this intermediate with an alcohol produces the alkoxide ion in the second step. In the last step the rearrangement of the tetrahedral intermediate gives rise to an ester and a DG. The process of transesterification is affected by various factors such as FFA levels and moisture, type of catalyst, alcohol to oil ratio and temperature (L.C. Meher, 2004). The literature states that, like the acid esterification step, this is a first order rate reaction and has a rate constant of 0.0078 min^{-1} (Siddharth Jain, 2011). Siddharth et al also report optimal reaction conditions at 50°C , 3:7 molar ratio of oil to methanol, 1% base catalyst by weight with a residence time of 180 mins, leading to an overall yield of 90.6% FAME. Figure 3.2 below presents the Transesterification reaction between triglyceride and methanol (Prachasanti Thaiyasuit, 2012).

Figure 3.2: Transesterification reaction between triglyceride and methanol (Prachasanti Thaiyasuit, 2012).

3.6.2 Enzyme-Catalysed route

It is similar to conventional transesterification process except the catalyst used is an enzyme such as lipase which can be obtained from microorganisms and fungi. The process is carried out in a non-aqueous environment with low operating conditions. In contrast to alkali and acid catalysed transesterification, enzyme catalysed do not form soaps and catalyses both triglycerides and FFA so extra cost is not incurred since it does not require a washing step. Feedstock containing high FFA are suitable for this process. However, their reaction rate is slower, and the cost of enzymes is expensive compared to alkalis and acids. Studies have shown that immobilising enzymes which is reducing the free movement of enzymes can decrease the production cost as it allows the enzyme to be reused (Parawara, 2009).

3.6.3 Supercritical transesterification

A catalyst free process that uses high temperature and pressure and alcohol to oil molar ratio to yield higher Methyl Ester content. A mixture of vegetable oil and alcohol are heated and pressurized to a level above their critical states and appear to be in a homogeneous phase. This leads to better heat and mass transfer and increased reaction time compared to the conventional catalyzed transesterification routes. It removes the pre-treatment step if high FFA oil is used since there is a simultaneous conversion of FFA and triglycerides to biodiesel. The glycerin produced is also of a superior quality, so minimum post-processing is required hence reducing overall production costs. However, this process is energy intensive with temperature up to more than 512.6 K and pressure 8.09 Mpa and though there are less equipment used, the harsh conditions might lead to erosion and fouling of equipment so materials designed to handle these can be costly (Chandra Shekhar Singh, 2021).

3.7 Economic Potential

The global production of biodiesel has a great economic potential as the world transitions away from fossil fuels. The biodiesel market was valued at approximately \$32.09 billion in 2021 and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 10% until 2030, reaching a value of \$75.67 billion (GVR, 2024). The market is driven by the global demand for renewable energy, and in the UK, with the issue of Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO) that requires the addition of biodiesel and bioethanol to petroleum-based products or paying a buy-out price per litre of obligation (Hugh Smith, 2013).

For biodiesel production, the feedstock cost can comprise up to 88% of the overall production expenses. Using WCO as a feedstock offers cost advantages as it is readily available, cheap in comparison to virgin oils which are generally expensive and reduces waste disposal expenses, supporting a circular economy. (S.N. Gebremariam, 2018)

Higher quality WCO can be sold to producers depending on the quality of the WCO. Collectors charge a higher quality WCO will cost around 45-60p/litre and lower quality for only 25p/litre. Furthermore, prices vary seasonally for the WCO. During the months in winter, biodiesel is reportedly used less in transport, or at lower blends, due to fears over the cold flowability of higher blends. Hence due to the low demand, biodiesel producers will pay about 40p/litre, or £400 - £500 per tonne in the winter months and more in the summer months around 60p/litre or between £600 and £700 per tonne. (S.N. Gebremariam, 2018)

Currently biodiesel costs around 75p/l to manufacture compared to petroleum-based diesel at 52p/l. If the criteria of biodiesel manufactured from 100% verified renewable sources such as WCO is met, producers are eligible for double RTFCs which are currently averaging around 12p per RTFC. If the RTFCs generate 24p/l this puts the biodiesel production at a 1p advantage to petroleum-based diesel, justifying the investment in the manufacturing capacity (Hugh Smith, 2013).

3.8 Business management considerations

To reach our required 600,000 tonnes per year quota, 676,710 tonnes of Waste Cooking Oil (WCO) and 1,189,345.2 tonnes of methanol are needed in order to produce 600,000 tonnes of annual capacity in biodiesel production. A portion of the methanol is recovered from a recovery system. Additionally, an annual demand for 56,126.064 tonnes of calcium oxide (CaO) and 9,850 tonnes of sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) is required. The process complies with mass conservation principles and has a byproduct in 72,012.11 tonnes of low-grade glycerol, an industrial compound. The glycerol obtained is saleable in its raw form or is processed further for increased economic value. Additional water is recovered in the process, which is then reused in-house within various processes within the plant but cannot be sold for commercial purposes.

Biodiesel market prices fluctuate depending on geopolitical factors. As of 2023 in Europe biodiesel has been valued at an average of \$1,400 per tonne, an output of 600,000 tonnes would generate a revenue of \$840,000,000 annually (Spglobal.com, 2024). However, the price of biodiesel is predicted to grow at a CAGR of 5% annually until the year 2030(www.grandviewresearch.com, 2024).

Low grade glycerol is sold at a wholesale price of \$200-\$300 per tonne, this is low unless the plant is to implement a glycerol purification section. However, a separate cost/ benefit analysis is needed to justify this operation. Taking the average as \$250 per tonne an output of 72,012.11 tonnes would generate a revenue of \$18,003,027.5 annually (Alerts, 2024).

The value of methanol fluctuates around \$500 per tonne, this is also influenced similarly as other Petro based chemicals as the industry as a whole is sensitive to geopolitical factors. At the average price stated previously the cost to obtain 1,189,245.2 tonnes of methanol will be \$594,622,600 annually. It is vital to note that the amount of methanol recovered is not accounted for in this estimate.

H₂SO₄ wholesale price are more stable at \$100 per tonne. This would mean a cost of \$985,000 annually.

CaO prices also fluctuate around \$100 per tonne which with the amount needed will cost \$561,206.4 per year (Alerts, 2024).

3.9 Health, safety, environmental and sustainable considerations

Biodiesel production involves a range of chemical processes which if improperly implemented can cause potential health, safety, environmental and sustainability challenges. This section will outline critical considerations to ensure safe handling, minimising environmental implications, and promotes a sustainable production process for producing biodiesel from WCO.

Health and safety risks:

In the production of biodiesel, several hazardous chemicals such as methanol, sulfuric acid, and calcium oxide are used which can pose as a potentially significant health and safety risk when not handled with proper protection and training.

Several chemicals used in making biodiesel have perilous properties due to their composition. Methanol is identified as highly combustible and toxic and can lead to major incidents of fires and harmful effects on health if misused. Sulfuric acid is considered an extremely corrosive substance that can cause severe burns if it meets skin or eyes and can also lead to respiratory irritation when its vapor is inhaled. Sodium hydroxide, or caustic, is another corrosive substance that can produce burns of a chemical nature and major injury to tissues that contact skin or eyes. Phosphoric acid may not be as toxic as sulfuric acid but can also cause irritation of skin and eyes and must thus be managed carefully. The use of these materials demands implementing stringent safety procedures that include proper use of appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE) in addition to adherence to proper storage and handling procedures in an endeavour to minimize risks in the production process. To work in a safe environment the use of PPE must be worn when handling these materials, rooms that are not located outside are to be well ventilated and have emergency precautions such as eye wash stations.

Considering environmental effects consist of the following: VOC emissions from methanol and other volatile substances in the system, as these contribute to air pollution. Due to us having a methanol recovery system, our process becomes more sustainable. Waste produced from the neutralised caustic gas (sodium hydroxide) must be properly disposed of to prevent harmful exposure to people and the environment. All materials must be handled with care to prevent spillages especially for corrosive substances in the process.

Materials in the process (e.g. methanol) are highly flammable therefore must be safely stored away from heat and to reduce environmental harm due to its toxicity. Both sulfuric and phosphoric acid are corrosive materials and need to be handled and stored safely.

Table 3.4 presents a benchmarking method using a simple risk to severity helping classify and rate each dangerous substance in the process. It is based on the severity (horizontal) compared to the likelihood of something to happen (vertical)

Table 3.4: Ranking table for material severity.

Chance of happening/ severity	1 - Negligible	2 - Minor	3 - Moderate	4 - Major	5 - Fatal
1 - Improbable	1	2	3	4	5
2 - Remote	2	4	6	8	10
3 - Occasional	3	6	9	12	15
4 - Probable	4	8	12	16	20
5 - Frequent	5	10	15	20	25

Table 3.5: Material rankings with justifications.

Material	Ranking	Justification
Methanol	2x5=10	Toxic and flammable material used in large volumes – use strict PPE
Oil	2x2=6	Generally stable however hot spills and slips can occur with improper handling
FAME	1x4=4	Stable with low toxicity and minimal interaction
Glycerol	2x3=6	Corrosive in high concentrations with lots of handling – PPE
H ₂ SO ₄	4x5=20	Highly corrosive – PPE and eye wash stations required at all times
NaOH	4x3=12	Highly caustic and can cause severe burns – PPE. Handled regularly – spill risk
H ₂ O	1x2=2	Only risk of spills or heat burns which are easily avoided
Oleic acid	2x3=6	Low toxicity – skin irritation - PPE
H ₃ PO ₄	3x3=9	Corrosive and can burn skin - PPE
Na ₃ PO ₄	3x3=9	Less handling and mildly corrosive – PPE eyewear and gloves

In conclusion the main materials to be wary of are anything scoring above a 9 (in the red zone) as these both cause a lot of harm and can occur often if proper safety is not maintained on site. These materials consist of methanol, H₂SO₄ and NaOH. As these are the main causes for concern a bow-tie diagram will be created to manage the risks. Figures 3.3 and 3.4 below illustrates the tools used to visualise the risks and key techniques that have been implemented to mitigate the dangers associated with handling hazardous substances.

Figure 3.3: Bow tie diagram for Sulfuric acid.

Figure 3.4: Bow tie diagram for Sodium Hydroxide.

3.10 Evaluation process selection

The selection of the acid-catalysed transesterification production route as the most suitable process was driven by a systematic assessment of numerous alternative pathways, including alkali-catalysed, enzyme-catalysed, and supercritical transesterification. The decision was executed based on feedstock abundance, economic feasibility, and environmental impact of each process as outlined in Chapter 2.

The acid-catalysed process showed high compatibility with the chosen feedstock, WCO. This is as the nature of WCO means the type of FFA present is highly variable depending on the type of cooking oil used which affects the prevalent carbon chain length, (Table 3.3). Conventional alkali-catalysed processes demonstrate higher economic feasibility however, due to this route requiring highly refined feeds with stringent FFA specifications, it is incompatible with the desired feedstock as saponification risks come into play. This introduces numerous complications such as, glycerol separation difficulties, and increased waste stream treatment costs (Prachasanti Thaiyasuit, 2012). In contrast, the acid-catalysed route transesterifies triglycerides and FFAs in one single reactor (transesterification reactor), which eliminates pretreatment requirements. This is a vital advantage as it enables the utilisation of low-cost, low quality WCO (Y Zhang, 2003).

The enzyme-catalysed process was established with environmental consideration in mind, which aligns with the modern transition of the industry towards a more sustainable future, and is compatible with varying FFA in the feedstock. However, the route was ruled out as a result of excessive catalyst costs. Immobilised lipase catalyst, despite being reusable, demanded an annual expense exceeding \$2 million for the required 600,000 tonnes of biodiesel output (Parawara, 2009). This completely eliminates the possibility of economic viability. Additionally, this route meant that the reactor sizing and the overall plant size would have had to be exceedingly large to meet the biodiesel production requirements due to the slower reaction times of 6-24 hours more compared to the acid-catalysed route (Parawara, 2009).

The supercritical transesterification route meant that the reaction could operate catalyst free, eliminating catalyst associated costs altogether. However, this meant an energy intensive process with excessive capital requirements. The operating conditions of 250 °C and 8 MPa (Chapter 3.6.3) would have required exotic and expensive alloys for the reactor vessel. This increased capital costs by 40% compared to standard stainless steel vessels (Metal, 2024). Additionally, the temperature of the reaction means the sustainability goals would have been undermined the energy required has a large carbon impact.

Further analysis proved the acid-catalysed route to be the most suitable route. Despite elevated methanol consumption relative to other process routes, an integration of a methanol recovery distillation column reduced methanol requirements to 6 % of the feedstock input (Y Zhang, 2003). Additionally, this process aligns with the 99.6% purity required by the European Biodiesel Board to enable forecourt sale. Lastly, this process also enables valorisation of glycerol, opening up another revenue stream. To summarise, the acid-catalysed route balances technical, economic, and regulatory requirements which were mentioned in the design basis section.

3.11 Site Study

For this site study, three primary locations were analysed:

- Discovery Park, Kent, United Kingdom
 - Southampton Science Park, United Kingdom
 - Nanjing Chemical Industry Park, China
- For each location, various factors were considered, outlined in the subheadings below.

Location and accessibility:

All three of the locations considered have excellent transport links, being established hubs of industry and innovation. Discovery Park for example is close to London, offering access to a major financial hub of Europe, as well as transport links via bus and train for employees. Access to raw materials is also adequate, with waste oil collection schemes running across the southeast, ensuring a steady supply of feedstock. The park also used to be home to a Pfizer plant, so much of the infrastructure required for distribution has already been developed.

Southampton Science Park is another domestic location suitable for biodiesel production on a large scale due to its proximity to major ports in Portsmouth, Southampton airport as well as excellent links by road via the M2 & M7. Similarly to Discovery Park, this location also has a dedicated bus service and good links via train.

Finally, Nanjing in the Jiangsu Province of China was investigated due to lower regional labour, resource and transportation costs, as well as it already being a hub of biofuel production. The Nanjing Chemical Industry Park already has partnerships with western companies such as *Currenta* and more widely the presence of reputable manufacturing companies such as BASF indicates strong viability for associated site costs and logistics considerations.

Environmental and regulatory considerations:

The two domestic locations both adhere to the same set of environmental and regulatory rules. In the UK, companies are required to register production with HMRC, and pay excise duty on production amounts over 2,500L/yr, as well as order permits regulated by the environment agency such as the Pollution Prevention and Control Permit and the Waste Management Licence. In addition, wider regulations such as the HSE act, COMAH and RTFO must be followed in order to ensure regulatory compliance. Finally, local planning permits would need to be obtained, though considering the status of the locations as science hubs with previous history of industrial processes, this should not pose an issue.

Information on environmental and regulatory considerations for Nanjing was harder to find than the two domestic sites due to a language barrier during research, although this does not serve to diminish the viability of the site. The local authority in Nanjing designates areas in which industrial activity is permitted, of which Nanjing Chemical Industry Park (NCIP) is one. Procurement of a license to operate in the area is promising, considering the area cultivated 128 industrial corporations in 2021 alone.

In addition to zoning regulation compliance, there are emissions mandates to follow. In 2021 the Chinese government established the Regulations on Management of Pollutant Discharge permits and considering the process specifics, these would need to be followed and obtained by the Nanjing Environmental Bureau so as to ensure environmental compliance. Additionally, comprehensive safety protocols and emergency response protocols are required by law, as outlined by the *National People's Congress for the People's Republic of China (NPCPRC, 2021)*, as well as the Guidelines for Chemical Process Safety Management (AQ/T 3034-2022, Yake, 2023).

Economic considerations:

Labour is a major consideration when it comes to operating a plant, so data from the Office for National Statistics was analysed for the two domestic sites, while a research paper including a market study was referenced for Nanjing. In Dover and Southampton, the average weekly salary was £506 and £550, respectively (Office for national statistics, 2015); in contrast, the labour cost for Nanjing is approximately 750RMB per week converting to £80 per week. Of course, from this data we can infer that China has a low standard and cost of living making it the most viable in this domain, but among the domestic locations Dover trails behind Southampton with a £44 difference.

In addition to labour considerations, location costs are a significant contributor to economic outlay. For the purposes of this study, costs of sites greater than 75,000 square feet were analysed to ensure that enough space would be offered for the necessary process units for the target of 600,000 tons of biodiesel per year. For the two domestic sites, online property websites served to provide a value for this market analysis; in Southampton, the price per square feet per year was calculated at £15 using an available property as reference. In Nanjing, the average price per square metre was calculated to be 1042RMB per square metre (CEIC, 2021) which converts to £10.65 per square foot per year.

Finally, there are economic benefits related to the areas in the form of tax breaks and deductions associated with innovative companies. For Kent, this is the Discovery Park zone, for Southampton this is the Solent zone and for Nanjing, there are reduced corporate tax rates of High and New Technology Enterprises (for which a biodiesel plant would qualify).

Site study conclusions:

After evaluating Discovery Park, Southampton Science Park, and Nanjing Chemical Industry Park, Southampton Science Park stands out as the best location for the biodiesel facility. Its excellent transport links, including proximity to major ports, Southampton Airport, and key motorways, ensure efficient logistics for feedstock and product distribution. A reliable raw material supply from southeast waste oil collection schemes further supports the plant plans for 600,000-tonne annual target.

Economically, Southampton offers competitive property prices at £15 per square foot per year and benefits from Solent tax incentives for innovative industries. While labour costs are slightly higher than in Kent, the robust infrastructure and financial perks of the site offsets this difference.

The regulatory framework is straightforward, and the industrial history of the park minimizes permitting challenges. In contrast, Nanjing, despite lower costs, presents risks like distance from European markets and potential difficulties navigating local regulations. The accessibility, infrastructure, and incentives of Southampton makes it the ideal choice for this project.

3.12 Plant Layout

Figure 3.5: Plant layout.

Dist.	Technical reference	Created by	Approved by
Chem Eng	2.2	Tom Pellegrino 11/04/2025	Tom Pellegrino
		Document type	Document state
		Finalised	
		File	DWG No.
		Lant layout	2.2
		Rev.	Date of issue
		14	24/4/25
		Sheet	1/1

List of equipment and schedule
Table 3.6: List of equipment and schedule.

EQUIPMENT ID	ROLE	TYPE EQUIPMENT	OF MATERIAL
E-101	Reactor 1 heat recovery	Heat exchanger	Stainless steel
E-201	Stream 202 heat recovery	Heat exchanger	Carbon steel
MIX-100	Recovered methanol & Methanol & H ₂ SO ₄ mixing	Mixer	Carbon steel
MIX-100A	Methanol & H ₂ SO ₄ mixing	Mixer	Carbon steel
P-101	Methanol & H ₂ SO ₄ pump	Pump	Stainless steel
P-102	WCO pump	Pump	Carbon steel
P-201	Recovered methanol pump	Pump	Carbon steel
R-101	Trans esterification reactor	CSTR (jacketed)	Stainless steel
R-201	Neutralisation of sulfuric acid	CSTR (jacketed)	Stainless steel
T-201	Methanol recovery distillation	Distillation	Carbon steel
T-301	Separates FAME from glycerol	Water washing	Stainless steel
T-401	FAME purification	Distillation	Carbon steel
T-501	Methanol and glycerol separation	Distillation	Carbon steel

Chapter 4. Mass and energy balances

Mass Balance on Mixing Tank (MIX-100)

Figure 4.1: MIX-100 diagram.

Type:	Mixing Tank
Objective:	In this tank, Methanol and Sulfuric acid are mixed before being fed into the transesterification reactor.
Catalyst:	Sulfuric acid
Pressure:	4 bar
Temperature:	80 °C

Table 4.4.1: Mix-100 stream conditions.

Operating Conditions	S1	S2	S3	S4
Temperature (°C)	25	81	25	74
Pressure (bar)	1	1.9	1	4

Table 4.2: Mix-100 mass balance.

Species	Inlet Streams		Outlet Streams		Mass Balance	
	S1	S2	S3	S4	In	Out
	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)
Methanol	581.47	3731.02		4313.82	138180.75	138180.75
Triacylglycerol						
Biodiesel						
Glycerol						
H ₂ SO ₄			114.70	114.27	11250.00	11250.00
H ₂ O						
CaO						
CaSO ₄						
Overall	581.47	3731.02	114.70	114.27	149430.75	149430.75

Mass Balance on Transesterification Reactor (R-101)

Figure 4.2: R-101 P&ID section.

Type: Transesterification Reactor

Objective: In this reactor, waste cooking oil enters and reacts with the catalyst and alcohol mixture to produce FAME and glycerol.

Catalyst: Sulfuric acid

Pressure: 4 bar

Temperature: 80 °C

Table 4.3: R-101 stream conditions.

Operating Conditions	S4	S5	S6	S7
Temperature (°C)	74	60	80	80
Pressure (bar)	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0

Table 4.4: R-101 mass balance.

Species	Inlet Streams		Outlet Streams		Mass Balance	
	S4	S5	S6	S7	In	Out
	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)
Methanol	4313.82			3968.71	138223.44	127165.48
Triacylglycerol		87.25		2.53	77250.00	2242.78
Biodiesel				184.61		75357.32
Glycerol				90.11		8298.28
H ₂ SO ₄	114.27			114.34	11207.31	11213.89
H ₂ O			133.39			2403.00
CaO						
CaSO ₄						
Overall	4428.09	87.25	133.39	4360.30	226680.75	226680.75

Mass Balance on Methanol Recovery Distillation (T-201)

Figure 4.3: T-201 P&ID section.

- Type:** Methanol Recovery Distillation Column
- Objective:** In this distillation column, 94% methanol is recovered and recycled back to R-101.
- Pressure:** 2 bar
- Temperature:** 108.8 °C

Table 4.5: T-201 stream conditions.

Operating Conditions	S7	S2	S8
Temperature (°C)	60	81	109
Pressure (bar)	4.0	1.9	2.0

Table 4.6: T-201 mass balance.

Species	Inlet Streams	Outlet Streams			Mass Balance	
	S7	S2	S8	In	Out	
	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	
Methanol	3968.71	3731.02	237.53	127165.48	127165.48	
Triacylglycerol	2.53		2.53	2242.78	2242.78	
Biodiesel	184.61		184.61	75357.32	75357.32	
Glycerol	90.11		90.11	8298.28	8298.28	
H ₂ SO ₄	114.34		114.34	11213.89	11213.89	
H ₂ O						
CaO						
CaSO ₄						
Overall	4360.30	3731.02	629.12	224277.75	224277.75	

Mass Balance on Neutralisation Reactor (R-201)

Figure 4.4: R-201 P&ID section.

Type: Neutralisation Reactor

Objective: In this reactor, Sulfuric acid is completely removed by adding calcium oxide (CaO) to produce CaSO₄ and H₂O.

Pressure: 2 bar

Temperature: 108.8 °C

Table 4.7: R-201 stream conditions.

Operating Conditions	S8	S9	S10	S11
Temperature (°C)	109	25	100	60
Pressure (bar)	2.0	1.01	1.01	1.3

Table 4.8: R-201 mass balance.

Species	Inlet Streams		Outlet Streams		Mass Balance	
	S8	S9	S10	S11	In	Out
	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)
Methanol	237.54			237.54	7,611	7610.93
Triacylglycerol	2.58			2.58	2,308	2307.99
Biodiesel	184.47			184.47	75,300	73884.75
Glycerol	89.27			89.27	8,221	8220.96
H ₂ SO ₄	114.25				11,206	
H ₂ O			111.48	103.83		3878.84
CaO		114.26			6,407	
CaSO ₄				114.60		15602.25
Overall	628.12	114.26	111.48	732.30	111,136	111135.59

Mass Balance on Separator (X-201)

Figure 4.5: X-201 P&ID section.

Type: Gravity Separator tank

Objective: In this Gravity Separator tank, Calcium Sulphate will be separated and removed from the mixture of FAME, glycerol, unconverted oil, methanol and water.

Pressure: 2 bar

Temperature: 108.8 °C

Table 4.9: X-201 stream conditions.

Operating Conditions	S11	S12	S13
Temperature (°C)	74	60	80
Pressure (bar)	4.0	4.0	4.0

Table 4.10: X-201 mass balance.

Species	Inlet Streams	Outlet Streams			Mass Balance	
	S11	S12	S13	In	Out	
	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	
Methanol	237.53		237.53	7610.97	7610.97	
Triacylglycerol	2.61		2.61	2308.44	2308.44	
Biodiesel	181.01		181.01	73884.75	73884.75	
Glycerol	89.26		89.26	8220.56	8220.56	
H ₂ SO ₄						
H ₂ O	103.83		103.83	1870.50	1870.50	
CaO						
CaSO ₄	114.60	114.60		15602.25	15602.25	
Overall	728.84	114.60	614.24	109127.25	109127.25	

Mass Balance on Water Washing Column (T-301)

Figure 4.6: T-301 P&ID section.

Type: Water Washing Column

Objective: In this Water washing column, FAME is separated from the glycerol, methanol and catalyst.

Pressure: 2 bar

Temperature: 25 °C

Table 4.11: T-301 stream conditions.

Operating Conditions	S13	S14	S15	S16
Temperature (°C)	56	50	60	56.4
Pressure (bar)	1.0	0.4	1.2	1.1

Table 4.12: T-301 mass balance.

Species	Inlet Streams		Outlet Streams		Mass Balance	
	S13	S14	S15	S16	In	Out
	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)
Methanol	237.53		236.77	0.75	7,611	7610.97
Triacylglycerol	2.61			2.61	2,308	2308.44
Biodiesel	181.01		0.14	184.32	73,885	73884.75
Glycerol	89.26		89.26		8,221	8220.56
H ₂ SO ₄						
H ₂ O	103.83	487.51	488.03	4.31	10,653	10653.00
CaO						
CaSO ₄						
Overall	614.24	487.51	814.20	191.98	102,308	102307.50

Mass Balance on Fame Purification Distillation Column (T-401)

Figure 4.7: T-410 P&ID section.

Type: FAME Purification Distillation Column

Objective: In this Distillation Column, FAME will be separated from water and methanol in the column overhead. Unconverted oil remained at the bottom of T-401 and taken out as a waste.

Pressure: 0.5 bar

Temperature: 462.6 °C

Table 4.13: T-401 Stream conditions.

Operating Conditions	S16	S17	S18	S19
Temperature (°C)	56	264	264	462.6
Pressure (bar)	1.0	0.4	0.4	0.5

Table 4.14: T-401 mass balance.

Species	Inlet Streams	Outlet Streams				Mass Balance	
	S16	S17	S18	S19	In	Out	
	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	
Methanol	0.75	0.75			23.92	23.92	
Triacylglycerol	2.61			2.61	2308.44	2308.44	
Biodiesel	184.32	0.67	183.21	0.01	75236.07	75236.07	
Glycerol							
H ₂ SO ₄							
H ₂ O	4.31	1.33	2.98		77.64	77.64	
CaO							
CaSO ₄							
Overall	191.98	2.75	186.19	2.61	77643.00	77643.00	

Mass Balance on Glycerol Purification Distillation Column (T-501)

Figure 4.8: T-501 P&ID section.

Type: Glycerol Purification Distillation Column

Objective: In this Distillation Column, Glycerol will be separated from water and methanol in the column.

Pressure: 0.5 bar

Temperature: 462.6 °C

Table 4.15: T-501 stream conditions.

Operating Conditions	S15	S20	S21
Temperature (°C)	60	52.6	107.3
Pressure (bar)	1.2	0.4	0.5

Table 4.16: T-501 mass balance.

Species	Inlet Streams	Outlet Streams			Mass Balance	
	S15	S20	S21	In	Out	
	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Molar Flowrate (kmol/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	Mass Flowrate (kg/h)	
Methanol	236.77	236.77		7586.58	7586.58	
Triacylglycerol						
Biodiesel	0.14		0.14	58.03	58.03	
Glycerol	89.26		89.26	8220.56	8220.56	
H ₂ SO ₄						
H ₂ O	488.03	410.64		8791.81	8791.81	
CaO						
CaSO ₄						
Overall	814.20	647.41	89.41	24664.50	24664.50	

Energy Balance on Transesterification Reactor (R-101)

Table 4.17: Inlet Energy Balance on Transesterification Reactor (R-101).

Species	Inlet Streams			
	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	4313.82	81.00	-49	-
Triacylglycerol	87.25	142.00	-35	-433611.35
Biodiesel		140.00		
Glycerol		130.00		
H ₂ SO ₄	114.27	138.00	-49	-764796.75
H ₂ O				
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				- 18145252.83

Table 4.18: Outlet Energy Balance on Transesterification Reactor (R-101).

Species	Outlet streams			
	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	3968.71	81.00	78	25074325.24
Triacylglycerol	2.53	142.00	78	28055.29
Biodiesel	184.61	140.00	55	1421522.80
Glycerol	90.11	130.00	55	644269.14
H ₂ SO ₄	114.34	138.00	45	710021.93
H ₂ O				
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				27878194.44

Energy Balance on Methanol Recovery Distillation (T-201)

Table 4.19: Inlet Energy Balance on Methanol Recovery Distillation (T-201).

Species	Inlet Streams			
	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	3968.71	81.00	-35	- 11251299.79
Triacylglycerol	2.53	142.00	-35	- 12588.91632
Biodiesel	184.61	140.00	-35	
Glycerol	90.11	130.00	-35	
H ₂ SO ₄	114.34	138.00	-35	- 552239.2829
H ₂ O				
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				- 11816127.99

Table 4.20: Outlet Energy Balance on Methanol Recovery Distillation (T-201).

Species	Outlet streams			
	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	237.53	81.00	84	1612305.71
Triacylglycerol	2.53	142.00	84	30213.39
Biodiesel	184.61	140.00	84	2171053.01
Glycerol	90.11	130.00	84	983974.70
H ₂ SO ₄	114.34	138.00	84	1325374.27
H ₂ O				
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				6122921.10

Energy balance on Neutralisation Reactor (R-201)

Table 4.21: Inlet Energy balance on Neutralisation Reactor (R-201).

Species	Inlet Streams			
	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	3968.71	81.00	-84	- 27003119.49
Triacylglycerol	2.53	142.00	-84	-30213.39
Biodiesel	184.61	140.00	-84	-2171053.01
Glycerol	90.11	130.00	-84	- 983974.7007
H ₂ SO ₄	114.34	138.00	-84	- 1325374.279
H ₂ O				
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				- 31513734.89

Table 4.22: Outlet Energy balance on Neutralisation Reactor (R-201).

Species	Outlet streams			
	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	237.53	81.00	35	673397.37
Triacylglycerol	2.53	142.00	35	12588.91
Biodiesel	184.61	140.00	35	904605.42
Glycerol	90.11	130.00	35	409989.45
H ₂ SO ₄	114.34	138.00	35	552239.28
H ₂ O				
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				2552820.45

Energy Balance on Fame Purification Distillation Column (T-401)

Table 4.23: Inlet Energy Balance on Fame Purification Distillation Column (T-401).

	Inlet Streams			
Species	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	1186.10	81.00	-31	-2978302.76
Triacylglycerol	156.57	142.00	-31	-689204.62
Biodiesel	0.50	140.00	-31	-2181.57
Glycerol		130.00	-31	
H ₂ SO ₄		138.00	-31	
H ₂ O	4.31	75.00	-31	-10020.53
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				-3679709.51

Table 4.24: Outlet Energy Balance on Fame Purification Distillation Column (T-401).

	Outlet streams			
Species	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	0.75	81.00	438	26460.27
Triacylglycerol	2.61	142.00	438	162153.62
Biodiesel	183.21	140.00	438	11234359.55
Glycerol	90.11	130.00	438	5130725.22
H ₂ SO ₄		138.00		
H ₂ O	2.98	75.00	438	
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				16553698.68

Energy Balance on Glycerol Purification Distillation Column (T-501)

Table 4.25: Inlet Energy Balance on Glycerol Purification Distillation Column (T-501).

	Inlet Streams			
Species	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	236.77	81.00	-35	-671242.40
Triacylglycerol		142.00	-35	
Biodiesel	0.14	140.00	-35	-696.60
Glycerol	89.26	130.00	-35	-406149.73
H ₂ SO ₄		138.00	-35	
H ₂ O	488.03	75.00	-35	-1281071.25
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				-2359160.00

Table 4.26: Outlet Energy Balance on Glycerol Purification Distillation Column (T-501).

	Outlet streams			
Species	Mol Flow Rate (Kmol/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kmol.K)	Temperature Difference (dt)	Enthalpy (KJ/hr)
Methanol	236.77	81.00	28	529322.58
Triacylglycerol		142.00	82	
Biodiesel	0.14	140.00	82	1632.04
Glycerol	89.26	130.00	82	951550.81
H ₂ SO ₄		138.00		
H ₂ O	410.64	75.00	27.6	850023.64
CaO				
CaSO ₄				
Overall				1482505.44

4.1 – BFD, PFD, &PI&ID

This section presents the engineering diagrams associated with this plant.

Figure 4.14: Block Flow Diagram.

Client: CCCU		Canterbury Christ Church University	
Title: Biodiesel Production Plant PFD			
Drawn by: Harry Lawson	Sheet:	Revision:	Date:
	PFD01	R03	9/5/2025

Process Description

This process chosen is acid-catalysed transesterification of waste cooking oil (WCO). The abundance of WCO as a waste product feedstock made this an appealing candidate for sustainability, cost and feedstock availability, further reasoning is outlined in chapter 3 and 7. The overall process is centred around four major unit operations: a transesterification reactor, a neutralization reactor for the acid catalyst, and two distillation columns for purification of the main fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) product and the glycerol by-product, which also serve as methanol recovery steps, all detailed in the chapter 4 figures. All chemical data is justified later in the chemistries section within chapter 3.

Feedstock handling and preparation

The waste cooking oil (WCO) feedstock is assumed to be partially pre-treated. Commercial WCO supply companies often offer services for drying the WCO as well as sediment removal, simplifying the overall process by requiring less unit operations and therefore less capital expenditure. Despite pre-treatment, free fatty acid (FFA) removal is not commonly offered by suppliers [This issue is solved through intelligent process selection, whereby the acid catalyst effectively deals with the FFA content by simultaneous esterification of FFAs and transesterification of triglycerides, thus mitigating saponification.

Transesterification

Transesterification is the core of the production process, converting the triglycerides in the oil to useful FAMES, using methanol as a reaction reagent. A high excess of 50:1 methanol to oil is required to drive the reversible reaction towards the desired FAME product. The utility of the sulphuric acid catalyst is twofold, since it serves as both a means to speed up the rate of reaction, as well as a means to remove FFAs which would interfere with FAME production through saponification side reactions, which would reduce overall yield and complicate separation processes. The methanol and acid catalyst are pre-mixed and heated up prior to feed into the transesterification reactor, while the WCO is directly fed into the reactor from storage tanks. It is imperative that the vessel is jacketed such that it maintains the ideal setpoint temperature of 80 °C required to increase the rate of reaction, without becoming so high as to degrade the FAMES and produce unwanted side reactions. The reactor is also pressurised at 4 bar and agitated to maintain efficient mass transfer, reducing dead zones and increasing reagent contacting. The resulting acidified FAME effluent is heated and fed into a distillation column for initial methanol recovery. Full detailed designs and specifications of this unit are available in chapter 6.

Catalyst removal

After distillation, the output heavy stream is fed to a heat exchanger with a setpoint of 60°C such that the stream matches the reaction conditions required inside the neutralisation reactor, thereby reducing utility load on the reactor. This feed is charged into the neutralisation reactor concurrently with the calcium oxide neutralisation agent, which exists in solid form and is charged into the reactor at room temperature using solid mass-transfer systems, which involve a rotary airlock valve, screw auger and hopper. Careful control of the feed of calcium oxide is required to prevent a runaway reaction due to exothermic surge. Similarly to the transesterification reactor, it is vital that the neutralisation reactor remains at the desired setpoint temperature and pressure of 60 °C and 2 bar such that the exothermicity is controlled. Both the careful and slow addition of calcium oxide catalyst as well as maintenance of reactor conditions prevent potentially catastrophic plant malfunctions.

The resulting neutralised FMAE-rich stream contains a calcium sulphate slurry, which requires further processing in a solid-liquid separator to remove and simplify downstream purification. In the same fashion, the resulting separated FAME mixture is then washed with water, so that the glycerol and FAME components may be separated into phases for feed into the final purification distillation columns. Full detailed designs and specifications of this unit are available in chapter 6.

Product purification and methanol recovery

The aqueous glycerol-rich stream and the FAME stream are fed into their respective distillation columns, which can achieve high product quality due to upstream processing efforts and considerations, in addition to recovering any remaining methanol for recycling. The FAME output is fuel-grade, however the glycerol byproduct remains crude as it is not the focus of the production process. Full detailed designs and specifications of these units are available in chapter 6.

Chapter 5. Energy recovery and utility balances

For energy-intensive operations such as biodiesel production via acid-catalysed transesterification, integrating heat recovery systems is essential in improving overall energy efficiency and reducing the overall operating costs. Process integration techniques, such as the use of heat exchanger networks, reduce the dependence on external utilities and allow for an effective energy reuse. Tools such as the Grand Composite Curve (GCC) as shown in [figure](#), is utilised to determine pinch points where the two curves come closest together and identify the optimal hot and cold utility targets.

In this acid-catalysed process which takes places in a CSTR, a significant opportunity for energy recovery lies in the thermal energy carried by the reactor output stream. As taken from the literature, (Y. Zhang, 2003), the reactor outputs a product stream at 80°C carrying (from calc). Meanwhile, the WCO requires (from calc) of thermal energy to be preheated from 25°C to 60°C.

A heat exchanger network (HEN) is considered to recover internal heat from the hot outgoing product stream and preheat the incoming feedstock, WCO to the desired reaction temperature of 80°C. Shell-and-tube or plate-type heat exchangers are often preferred due to their ability to handle viscous fluids and facilitate easy maintenance (Ma and Hanna, 1999)

Table 5.1: Heat exchanger network energy balance.

Streams	Materials	Flow Rate (kg/hr)	Specific Heat (kJ/kg·K)	Inlet Temp (°C)	Final Temp (°C)	Heat Input (KJ/hr)	(KW)
Cold	Waste Cooking Oil	77250	1.97	60	80	3043650	845
Cold	Waste Cooking Oil	77250	1.97	25	60	5326388	1480
Hot	Methanol	127165.4843	2.51	80	70	3191854	887
Hot	Waste Cooking Oil	2242.7775	1.97	80	70	44183	12
Hot	Biodiesel	75357.324	2.2	80	70	1657861	461

From table 5.1, the total amount of heat load that can be provided to heat the WCO is 1496KW and the heat load needed to raise the temperature from 25 °C to 60 °C for the WCO is 1480KW. There is sufficient heat recovery to be utilised to heat the incoming WCO up so a heat exchanger can be integrated to do so but only until 60 °C where afterwards the preheated oil requires another additional heat load of 845KW to raise the temperature to required temperature in the reactor at 80°C as shown in figure after the pinch point. This shows that less amount of external heating is needed since a significant amount of it has been reduced with the use of a heat exchanger, ensuring less dependency on external utilities for heating.

Figure 5.1: Composite Curve.

Chapter 6. Equipment design

6.1 Major equipment 1

Design of Transesterification reactor (R-101)

For the transesterification of waste cooking oil (WCO) into biodiesel (FAME) using sulfuric acid as a homogeneous catalyst, a CSTR is selected based on its ability to handle liquid-phase reactions involving high FFA feedstocks and to provide uniform mixing and temperature control, which are essential for achieving high conversion rates. The design is informed by kinetic data and process parameters from literature, (Y. Zhang, 2003), ensuring a practical and scalable system. Key design considerations include catalyst concentration, methanol-to-oil molar ratios, reactor volume, conversion efficiency, and material compatibility with the acidic environment.

Catalyst Selection

Sulfuric acid is commonly employed as a catalyst in the biodiesel production process, particularly when feedstocks such as WCO containing high levels of FFA are used due to their ability to enhance biodiesel yields as it prevents soap formation and maintains the desired reaction pathway. They have a high boiling point of 337°C making it stable and allow for sustained reaction rates. Concentration used is at a range of 1.5–3.5 mol% as adapted from the study by (Y. Zhang, 2003), with molar ratio of 1.3:1 for sulfuric acid to WCO at mass flow rates supplied, 11,207kg/hr and 77,250kg/hr respectively.

Selectivity and Yield

The process achieved a high conversion efficiency, with 97% of the waste cooking oil assumed to be converted into FAME within 4 hours from (Y. Zhang, 2003). High proportions of methanol are used to promote equilibrium conversions of oil to esters with a methanol-to-oil molar ratio of 50:1, total methanol at a mass flow rate of 138,223kg/hr.

Reaction Kinetics

Kinetic parameters are derived based on the literature (Y. Zhang, 2003), assuming pseudo-first-order behaviour. The kinetic constant, k is calculated to be 0.0146 min^{-1} and hence the reaction rate equation is given as $-r_A = 0.0146C_A$ where C_A is the concentration of WCO. This is found via the equation, $-\ln \frac{C_A}{C_{A0}} = kt$ which is converted to the equation, $X = 1 - e^{-kt}$ where X , conversion and time, t given to be 97% and 240 minutes respectively are substituted to find the kinetic constant. Handwritten calculations are provided in appendix.

Design Equation of CSTR

From the design equation, $V = \frac{FAO \cdot X}{r_A}$ where FAO is the initial molar flow rate of the WCO, the volume of the CSTR is calculated to be 3,135.59 m³ which is impractical for one CSTR so two CSTRS will be put into place in series to cut down the volume and to achieve an overall of 97% conversion. To make the design more practical, the total volume is split equally between two reactors in series. Thus, the volume for each CSTR becomes:

$$V_1 = V_2 = \frac{3,135.59}{2} = 1,567.79\text{m}^3$$

To achieve the desired overall conversion of 97%, each reactor is designed to achieve 82.7% conversion. This ensures that the combined conversion from both reactors gives the target 97%. The relationship is given by:

$$\text{Overall Conversion} = 1 - (1 - X_1) \times (1 - X_2)$$

Where X_1 and X_2 are the conversion rates for Reactor 1 and Reactor 2, respectively. For 82.7% conversion in each reactor, the overall conversion will equal to 97% overall.

The residence time is approximately 1,135 minutes from equation: $t = V/v_o$ where V is the total reactor volume in one reactor and v_o which is 1.414.85m³/min.

Dimensions of CSTR

To maintain the same mixing behaviour as the pilot plant in the study, the full-scale CSTRs use an H/D ratio of 3:1 (Y. Zhang, 2003). The height and diameter are calculated using the volume of a vertical cylinder: $V = \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \times H$, where D is the diameter of the reactor and H, the height. Given the H:D ratio is 3:1, the height can be expressed as $H = 3D$, and substituting this into the equation gives: $D = \sqrt[3]{\frac{4V}{3\pi}}$, where diameter is calculated to be 8.73m and the height to be 26.19m.

Material of Construction

The transesterification reactor (R-101) is designed as a stainless steel (type 316) vessel to ensure adequate corrosion resistance against sulfuric acid at the given operating conditions.

Hydraulic Design of R-101/Equipment Specification Sheet

Table 6.1: Equipment specification sheet R-101.

Reactor Equipment Specification Sheet	
Author	Misa Gurung
Item code	R-101
Type	Jacketed Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor
Reactor Design	
Height, H	26.19 m
Diameter, D	8.73 m
Reactor Volume	41.7m ³
Operating conditions	
Temperature	80°C
Pressure	4 Bar
Agitator Speed	400 rpm
Operating mode	Continuous
Materials of Construction	
Vessel	Stainless Steel (type 316)
Agitator	Stainless steel (type 316)

6.2 Major equipment 2 - neutralisation reactor

The neutralisation unit is vital to reducing downstream corrosion, therefore it is critical to take care during design. This unit utilises solid calcium oxide to react with the acidic biodiesel, forming a slurry of calcium oxide and calcium sulphate in addition to water. The reaction and other details are outlined in chapters 4 and 3.

Sizing methodology

The scientific literature indicates that near-complete conversion may be achieved using an appropriate excess of calcium oxide, approximately 97-99%. Therefore, design calculations may be simplified by the use of residence time data gathered from literature. A common residence time for this type of reaction in this context was found to be 30 mins, however fouling and scaling must be accounted for, so a conservative safety factor of 2 is applied, giving a 60 min residence time.

Table 6.2: Equipment specification sheet R-201.

Reactor Equipment Specification Sheet	
Author	Harry Lawson
Item code	R-201
Type	Jacketed Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor
Reactor Design	
Height, H	1.54 m
Diameter, D	0.94 m
Reactor Volume	0.93 m
Operating conditions	
Temperature	60°C
Pressure	2 Bar
Agitator Speed	300
Operating mode	Continuous
Materials of Construction	
Vessel	Stainless Steel (type 316)
Agitator	Stainless steel (type 316)

Client: CCCU	Canterbury Christ Church University		
Title: Neutralisation reactor spec sheet			
Drawn by: Harry Lawson	Sheet:	Revision:	Date:
	SH02	R02	6/5/2025

6.3 Major equipment 3

The most crucial equipment addressed herein is a continuous distillation column, which is specifically tailored to separate glycerol from the methanol–glycerol–water stream generated in biodiesel production. The separation is required for product quality and environmental specifications, allowing the recuperation of valuable methanol and elimination of excess water and by-products. The feed in the column includes a total of around 847.08 kmol/hr of methanol, water, and glycerol. For simplicity of column modelling and design calculations, the system was assumed to be a binary methanol–water system and glycerol as the heavy component due to its low volatility. The assumption is reasonable considering the large differences in boiling points and non-azeotropic nature of the mixture.

Vapour–liquid equilibrium data were acquired by generating them through Antoine constants, and thermodynamic properties were acquired or estimated via Aspen modelling and enthalpy correlation equations. The column is run at a pressure of 40 kPa and processes streams under relatively gentle thermal conditions, i.e., temperatures of 52.6°C to 107.3°C. The design is 7 trays with a 0.5 m spacing, which gives a total column height of 4.5 m and a diameter of 4.39 m. Sieve trays were chosen due to the fact that they are cost-effective, simple to maintain, and efficient to deal with systems having big volatility distinctions, e.g., methanol–water.

316L stainless steel was utilized for the downcomer and trays. While the chemical environment is relatively benign, the residual water and acids present in the stream represent a risk of long-term corrosion. 316L grade has good resistance to this type of degradation, along with high-temperature strength and cleanliness of operation—a nice combination of properties for a continuously operating system with only 5 days/year shutdown. According to the process demand of 24.9 m³/h at 120 kPa and 60 °C, the Grundfos CR 15-4 pump is not appropriate because it is beyond the optimum flow range of the unit, where its efficiency and reliability of operation may be impaired.

The most suitable choice is the Grundfos CRN 32-2 pump that will effectively address the desired flowrate value all while still operating efficiently. This model is offered with 316L stainless steel wetted materials for improved chemical resistance to methanol, glycerol, and trace acidic by-products typically found in biodiesel feed streams (Evoqua, 2025). CRN 32 also provides good head generation with improved correlation to the duty point required, and the compatibility of EPDM seals promotes longevity in hot polar solvent service (Methanol Institute, 2016). This choice enhances long-term reliability, chemical resistance, and energy efficiency for continuous running of the glycerol purification column.

Figure 6.1: T-501 P&ID section with control loops

Table 6.3: T-501 Feed pump load sheet

Pump Load Sheet		
Item Number	4	
Item Name	Feed Pump	
Supporting Calculations	On page	
Pump Type	Magnetic Centrifugal	
Stage Number	1	
Fluid Composition	ID	
	Methanol	36.30%
	Water	63.70%
Suction	Temperature (oC)	77
	Pressure (bar)	1.01
Normal Capacity (m3/hr)	81.84	
Maximum Capacity (m3/hr)	206.29	
Estimated efficiency	70%	
Power (W)	82.2	
Notes: Corrosion		

Figure 6.2: T-501 Sieve tray design.

Figure 6.3: T-501 Equipment data specification sheet.

Table 6.4: T-501 Sieve tray specifications.

Plate No	2	Turndown	65% of max rate
Plate I.D. (m)	1.86	Plate Material	Carbon Steel
Hole Size	3	Downcomer	316L Stainless Steel
Hole Spacing	5	Plate Spacing (m)	0.5
Hole Pitch	25	Plate Thickness (mm)	9
		Active Holes	12,874

Table 6.5: T-501 Equipment Data Specification Sheet.

EQUIPMENT DATA SPECIFICATION SHEET			
Item name	Distillation Column	Supporting Calculation	App. 1.3
Author	Jack Wyatt	Design Version	1.1
DESIGN DATA			
Design Temperature		308.5	K
Operating Temperature		333.2	K
Design Pressure		1.20	Bar
Operating Pressure		0.40	Bar
Mode of Operation	Continuous		
Operation Type	Isothermal		
Dimensions			
Cross Sectional Area		15.16	m
Inner Diameter		4.39	m
Outer Diameter		4.394	m
Wall Thickness		2.24	mm
Column Height		4.50	m
Constructional Material			
Column	316L Stainless Steel		
Downcomer	316L Stainless Steel		
Plates	316L Stainless Steel		
Stream conditions			
Feed			
	847.08	kmol/hr	
	333.2	K	
	1.20	Bar	
Bottoms			
	165.99	kmol/hr	
	380.5	K	
	0.50	Bar	
Distillate			
	644.44	kmol/hr	
	325.8	K	
	0.40	Bar	

6.4 Major equipment 4 (T-401)

The major equipment outlined in this section is a distillation column.

The final stage in a biodiesel production plant is purifying the product to meet regulatory standards of 99.6% purity by removing any residual reactants or by-products of the reaction. A continuous distillation column is designed to purify a stream of 328 kmol/hr consisting of mostly FAME and triacylglycerol.

It is vital to note that few initial assumptions were made to enable the calculations. The distillation column was modelled as a binary system by combining FAME and H₂O to create pseudo-component as the presence of H₂O in the feed stream is extremely low at a mass fraction of 0.0001 (Y. Zhang et al., 2003). This also simplifies calculations. As FAME and triacylglycerol are mixtures with various constituents, the mixture thermodynamic data are not available. Therefore, by representing each component with one constituent the thermodynamic data can be found.

The plate and downcomer material chosen was 316L grade stainless steel. This is as although the components present are relatively noncorrosive, the feed contains traces of water and other by-products from the reaction stage which are mildly acidic. Over time this will lead to corrosion. This grade of stainless steel is designed to tolerate these conditions. The stainless steel is also rated to withstand the temperature and pressure in the column. Additionally, with the low downtime per year being 5 days, the ease of cleaning for this material will facilitate swiftness in the operation.

The feed pump requirements were calculated and presented in Appendix 3.1. The calculations concluded that a pump with a power output of 33.40 W capable of displacing 80.82 m³/hr is required. Therefore, an “off the shelf” generic pump was selected to be the Grundfos CR 15-4. This pump is designed for chemically resistant applications, which is required with the column feed. The flow capacity also accommodates the design specifications as the pump is rated for capacities in the range of 50–100 m³/hr. Additionally, the pump is magnetically driven, which minimises leakage and maintenance.

Table 6.6: T-401 Column mass balance.

Mol flow rate (kmol/hr)			Composition (mol fraction)		
Feed	Distillate	Bottoms	Feed	Distillate	Bottoms
7.18	2.34	4.83	0.03	0.01	0.97
320.89	320.75	0.14	0.97	0.99	0.03
328.00	323.00	5.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 6.7: T-401 Feed pump load sheet

Pump load sheet		
Item No.	3	
Item name	Feed pump	
Supporting calcs. On page		
Pump type	Magnetic centrifugal	
Stage No.	1	
Fluid composition	ID	
	FAME	96%
	Triacylglycerol	4%
Suction	Temperature (C)	56.4
	Pressure (Bar)	0.5
Normal capacity (m ³ /hr)	80.82	
Maximum capacity (m ³ /hr)	100	
Estimated efficiency	70%	
Power (W)	33.39	
Notes : Fluid acidic		

Table 6.8: T-401 Sieve tray design.

Table 6.9: T-401 Sieve tray specifications.

Plate Number	1	Turndown	60% of max rate
Plate I.D. (m)	2.15	Plate material	316L Stainless Steel
Hole size (mm)	12	Downcomer	316L Stainless Steel
Hole-pitch (mm)	20-25	Plate spacing	0.6 m
Total no. holes	109,694	Plate thickness	5 mm
		Plate pressure drop	98.47 mm liquid

Figure 6.4: T-401 specification sheet.

Table 6.10: T-401 condenser specification.

Heat exchanger specification					
Item name	Column condenser	Item No.	1		
Total surface area	141.71	m ²	Author	Tom Pellegrino	
No. of shells used	1				
Surface area per shell	141.71	m ²			
Performance of one shell					
Fluid name		Water		FAME vapour	
Allocation		Tube side		Shell side	
		In	Out	In	Out
Fluid flow	Total	kg/hr			
Vapour		67,544.20			
liquid			67,544.20	84,996	84,996
Temperature	°C	236.8	195	15	30
Operating pressure	Bar	0.5			
Design pressure	Bar	0.5			
Fouling resistance	m ² K/W	0.0005		0.0002	
Heat transfer coefficient				kW/m ² °C	
Mean temperature difference (Corrected)			°C		
Heat transfer duty (per shell)			kW		
Materials of construction		Tubes	Cupro-nickel		
		Shell			
Type		Horizontal shell			
No. of tubes in bundle		473	No. of tube passes		2
Tube : OD 19.05 mm , ID 16.6 mm , Length 5 m					
Tube arrangement Triangular , Tube-tube pitch 1.25					
Shell : OD 844 mm , ID 833 mm		No. of shell passes		1	
Baffle cross type : Single segmental, horizontal cut				% cut spacing	20
Baffle-longitudinal ; N/A				Design code	1.14
Sketch					
Remarks					

The distillation column designed in this project outlines an effective, traditional approach to separating biodiesel from reactant residues, yielding a high purity distillate which conforms to fuel standards. The method was based on the McCabe-Thiele model for the preliminary values which were then used in ASPEN to simulate more accurate results. The results from calculations yielded a 12 meter high column with a 2.18 m outer diameter made of 316L stainless steel, which treats a feed of 71,114 kg/hr purifying it to 99% FAME. The hydraulic and mechanical designs of the column are also presented. A heat exchanger designed to bring the feed to boiling point is designed as a one shell-pass two tube-pass exchanger with novel tube materials made specific for the shell-side fluid. Overall, the calculations are presented in full and critically evaluated with common industry practices as the benchmark offering a detailed, successful distillation column design.

Table 6.11: T-401 feed preheater specification.

Heat exchanger specification				
Item name	Feed heater	Item No.	2	
Total surface area	125.58 m ²	Author	Tom Pellegrino	
No. of shells used	1		Supporting calcs. Major design document	
Surface area per shell	123.58 m ²			
Performance of one shell				
Fluid name	Heating oil		Column feed	
Allocation	Tube side		Shell side	
	In	Out	In	Out
Fluid flow Total	kg/hr			
Vapour				
liquid	307,440	307,440	71,114.2	71,114.2
Temperature	°C	300	260	56.4
Operating pressure	Bar	0.5		
Design pressure	Bar	0.5		
Fouling resistance	m ² K/W	0.0001		0.0005
Heat transfer coefficient		826.45		kW/m ² °C
Mean temperature difference (Corrected)		65.83 °C		
Heat transfer duty (per shell)	6,832.30	kW		
Materials of construction	Tubes	Nickel coated copper		
	Shell	SA-516 Gr. 70 standard carbon steel		
Type		Horizontal shell		
No. of tubes in bundle	692	No. of tube passes	2	
Tube : OD 19.05 mm	, ID 16.6 mm		, Length 5 m	
Tube arrangement	Triangular		, Tube-tube pitch 1.25	
Shell : OD 1003.17 mm	, ID 993.17 mm		No. of shell passes	1
Baffle cross type : Single segmental, horizontal cut			%cut spacing	25
Baffle-longitudinal ; N/A			Design code	2.14
Sketch				

Chapter 7. Sustainability and environmental protection

To analyse the sustainability of the process and its effects on the environment, both local and global, a life cycle analysis approach has been taken, examining the impacts of all relevant factors from cradle to gate. Through this framework, it is possible to not only gain insight into the environmental implications of a running plant, but it is also possible to gain insight into the implications of factors such as construction, transport, feedstock sourcing, energy and utility consumption, waste generation and even decommissioning. The analysis of such factors allows for an overall conclusion regarding practical sustainability to be reached.

Regulatory Framework

The regulatory climate underlying biodiesel manufacture from waste cooking oil (WCO) in the UK and EU is currently favourable but prone to future fluctuation as the landscape is constantly evolving. WCO, as defined by the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED) and the UK Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO), is a "double-counting" feedstock and thus can be utilized for two Renewable Transport Fuel Certificates (RTFCs) per litre due to dual purpose. WCO is now commonly treated as a "zero-burden" input in life cycle analyses, with no upstream emissions assigned to its manufacture, which is a central assumption behind useful carbon intensity metrics.

The plant's location near delicate ecosystems like the river Itchen necessitate full-scale environmental impact analyses under the Town and Country Planning regulations of 2017 due to its status as a Special Conservation Area. This includes mitigation strategies for emissions, water and all chemical waste. Specifically, environmental permitting as per the Environmental Permitting Regulations of 2016; this permit is awarded by the environmental agency (EA) under conditions such as following the Best Available Techniques (BAT) guidelines to prevent and minimise contamination of the surrounding environment via industrial runoff. Emission Limit Values (ELVs) are also derived from BAT guidelines as detailed in reference documents (BREF).

Further, water discharge must be managed and negotiated with the EA, with common values including the maintenance of 20mg/L biochemical oxygen demand, 125mg/L chemical oxygen demand, 10mg/L total nitrogen and limitation of phosphorous to 1mg/L, methanol to 1mg/L and sulphates to 500mg/L. However, these values are flexible according to a variety of factors usually established during negotiation. Water nutrient neutrality is of critical importance.

As stated previously, a full-scale environmental impact analysis in collaboration with the EA is almost certainly required for a plant of this scale and use case. This must include analysis of impact to local air quality, water availability, biodiversity and noise within the Southampton site area.

Feedstock and Supply Chain

The zero burden regulatory classification of WCO in lifecycle analysis significantly reduces overall carbon impact, though it is important to consider transport costs of large quantities of WCO, as well as all other reagents. The scale likely puts the plant under scope 3 greenhouse gas emissions, which means a deeper analysis is required on the efficiency of transport vehicles and the maximum optimal range WCO can be collected from before significantly increasing carbon impact beyond acceptable thresholds.

Methanol is another significant reagent in the process since it is used at a 50:1 excess, as detailed in chapter 3. This means the annual demand is over a million tonnes. However, a significant portion of that is recycled and may be used continuously, adding cost and carbon expenditure but overall reducing carbon impact compared to having to transport such large quantities.

The last major reagent in terms of carbon impact is the calcium oxide neutralisation agent, however as a relatively dense solid, transportation is far less carbon intensive than WCO and methanol, especially considering the comparative quantities outlined in the mass and energy balance within chapter 4.

Emissions and Utility Consumption

Methanol as a volatile organic compound (VOC) is a major concern regarding air pollution, especially in the event of an emergency. Methanol is present throughout the process meaning multiple potential points of failure, therefore special care is necessary when examining the potential impact to the environment. The use of scrubbers around specific high-risk units would be prudent, and recognised by regulatory bodies as an effort to achieving minimal environmental impact.

It is also important to consider the reboilers that are used across the multiple distillation columns in the process, as detailed in the chapter 4 PFD, which have a non-negligible impact on carbon impact due to the need for a heat source, likely combustion. The heat duty required is likely to be very high, according to the values given in chapter 5. Low nitrogen oxide boilers are a potential solution to this problem, although use should be selective due to increased maintenance cost as well as capital cost.

It is highly recommended from a liability limitation and environmentally conscious position to perform atmospheric dispersion modelling for all major sources of emission, including the heaters from the distillation columns, reactors and other process units. This will allow insight out into the potential for increase of particulate matter in reference to the nearest sensitive emissions sensor.

Additionally, comprehensive analysis of the local water supply will have to be performed in conjunction with the EA and southern water, so as to ensure no overburden occurs. This is integral due to the number jacketed reactors in the process, as well as the need for continuous condensation of methanol for recycle. Efficient grey water waste management systems will need to be produced, either through the installation of treatment systems on-site or outsourcing to a disposal company. The former method allows for discharge into the nearby river Itchen, however both the initial and ongoing costs may be significant, as continued monitoring of the river nutritional profile would have to be performed.

Finally, the sheer scale of the plant requires a very high energy load, as detailed in chapters 4, 5 and 6. Due to the significant power consumption of the plant for cooling and heating purposes, it would be economical to consider a full-scale PINCH system so as to utilize waste heat. The exothermic nature of the neutralisation reactor makes this a particularly appealing idea, considering it will be a constant source of heat via the fundamental chemical reaction occurring.

Waste Generation

Calcium sulphate is a main waste product with over 100,000 tonnes per year, and it is discharged after the neutralisation reactor as a slurry. The nature of this waste product (slurry) makes disposal and handling more hazardous both to health and to the environment, as rates of leaching increase. Thus, appropriate waste disposal techniques must be generated, whether that be by using a disposal company or by on-site treatment allowing for simple disposal.

All other waste products are minimal in comparison, with unconverted oil being the next major source of waste due to conversion efficiency issues. Fortunately, this stream is easily recycled back into the process, allowing higher conversion to be achieved on a long-term timescale, increasing product output.

Finally, as mentioned above, wastewater sludge is another significant form of waste in the process, though mostly non-hazardous. Further, wastewater disposal options are plentiful, and the field of treatment within chemical engineering is well-established, with on-site treatment options frequently utilised by large companies. Recovery to reduce water burden on the local area is preferable, although this may increase capital and operating costs beyond feasible thresholds.

Circular Economy Opportunities

Crude glycerol is produced as a byproduct, and is inherently recovered in the process to a degree that would allow sale, therefore reducing overall carbon impact of producing the biodiesel, as the impact of the whole process would then be split between the two products. Crude glycerol is a commonly sought reagent with a sizeable market demand. This dual-purpose process increases appeal to regulatory bodies also, considering it shows an effort to recover useful materials instead of simply discarding and having another factory produce glycerol specifically, which significantly increases greenhouse gas emissions.

Similarly to crude oil, it is possible to treat the calcium sulphate waste product for sale to construction and agriculture companies, however this is not considered in the process design. Nonetheless, it is worth considering from a lifecycle analysis standpoint and warrants the investigation into feasibility via a feasibility study to analyse both economic potential as well as carbon possible impact reductions.

Furthermore, as discussed previously, the nature of the cooling and heating demand in the process validates PINCH as a viable measure to reduce costs and overall environmental impact, but this should be weighed against increased water fouling rates.

Lifecycle Impact Evaluation and Conclusions

The lifecycle analysis of the 600,000-tonne output biodiesel plant at the Southampton Science Park indicates areas of positive sustainability implementation that align with both environmental requirements as well as economic requirements, however it also highlighted challenges that would have to be diligently considered and investigated in greater depth. The classification of WCO as zero burden by regulatory bodies significantly improves the viability of biofuel in place of fossil fuel from a carbon impact and lifecycle analysis perspective, and the secondary revenue streams from glycerol and calcium sulphate further bolster the position that the acid catalysed process is worth considering for large-scale production.

In spite of this, the practical sustainability of the plant depends heavily on intelligent engineering design as well as efficient navigation of the regulatory system. Carbon impact upstream still significantly impacts the overall process, with methanol and sulphuric acid being particularly burdensome in their production. Controlling the environmental release of effluent methanol is of paramount importance to the end of preventing damage to the local area. Furthermore, advanced wastewater management techniques are equally important so as to prevent pollution to the river Itchen.

Additionally, the significant energy demand poses a challenge for maintaining an acceptable carbon footprint, nonetheless engineering strategies such as PINCH technology or the utilisation of renewable energy sources could offer productive solutions in minimising impact but require deeper investigation.

Overall, the biggest opportunity to improvement of the environmental impact of the process without considering a full redesign is the valorisation of calcium sulphate, which offers not only a tertiary revenue stream but a cost-efficient and environmentally friendly method of waste disposal, without the use of landfill. In conclusion, the long-term sustainability of the plant depends on applying robust engineering solutions and stable regulatory and supply chain support of WCO, and the resulting localised impacts of the process on the surrounding environment.

Chapter 8. Process safety

A HAZOP study has been conducted around the neutralisation reactor and associated feed cooling unit. This ensures key process steps remain safe and comprehensively evaluated for potential safety hazards, as well as barriers to smooth operation. A variety of nodes were assigned each component of the reactor, including feed and effluent lines, valves, reaction vessel, jacket and many more.

The most significant hazards identified were the loss of feed, overfeeding of either input leading to flooding or a runaway reaction, backflow issues leading to rapid exothermic reaction and pressure buildup. All of these have the potential to cause catastrophic incidents within a chemical plant, with a likelihood of fatality if not prevented, mitigated and managed correctly.

Safeguards such as interlocks, bursting discs and alarms were identified as potential control measures, with additional suggestions on improving flow control, installing redundant sensors and robust maintenance protocols.

This HAZOP study highlights the importance of comprehensive, systematic and quantitative hazard analysis for the purposes of ensuring a safe and sustainable production plant.

Project title		Detailed design of a biodiesel neutralisation reactor and relate						Document number:		HAZOP01	
Location		Southampton									
Project Number:		3						Design intent:			
Client		CCCU						To provide a continuously stirred and temperature-controlled environment where sulfuric acid reacts with calcium hydroxide to neutralise free acid from the acidified biodiesel stream.			
System Considered:		Reference:		Item:							
Neutralisation Reactor		SIN3		Reaction vessel							

Item	Guide Word	Deviation	Cause	Consequence	Safe Guards	Impact to.	Severity	Likelihood	Impact rating	Recommendations			
1	None	No mixing	Agitator failure, motor trip, power loss	Solids settle, reaction uneven means hot spots, fouling	Agitator status alarm, interlock to feeds	Equipment	4	3	12	Add trip on agitator status to halt acid/base feeds			
2	More	Excessive agitation	Control loop failure, VFD fault	Vortex formation, air ingress means pH instability	Speed feedback loop	Product quality	2	2	4	Set speed limits in drive control			
3	Less	Inadequate mixing	Motor under torque, high slurry load	Dead zones, incomplete reaction means product quality loss	Load monitor, torque feedback	Process efficiency	3	3	9	Match agitator size to solids load, alarm on high torque.			
4	High Temp	Reactor temperature too high	Cooling failure, runaway reaction	Overpressure, boiling, flash vaporisation	High temp alarm, trip on acid feed	Human safety	5	3	15	Emergency cooling loop or quench injection			
5	Low Temp	Temperature too low	Overcooling, jacket overshoot, incorrect	Gypsum crystallisation, reaction stalls	Low-temp alarm, jacket bypass	Product quality	3	3	9	Tighten control range, insulate vessel			
6	Other than	Incorrect pH or chemical imbalance	Mis-dosed reagents, sensor drift	Corrosion or incomplete neutralisation	Inline pH probe, calibrated daily	Environmental	4	2	8	Redundant pH sensors, regular calibration			
7	As well as	Foam formation	Organics in feed, CO ₂ from impurities	Level probe false reading, vent fouling	Foam trap, anti-foam agent dosing	Operational safety	2	3	6	Dose antifoam automatically if foaming starts			
8	Reverse	Flow reversal in vessel outlet	Blocked discharge, suction from downstream	Slurry backflows means dogging, contamination	NRV at outlet line	Equipment	3	2	6	Add NRV and suction break in downstream line			
9	Blockage	Solids buildup in vessel bottom	Low agitation, poor geometry	Decreased volume, thermal hotspots, fouling	Flush port, conical base	Maintenance burden	3	3	9	Increase agitation or install blade extensions			
10	High Pressure	Overpressure in reactor	Excess gas (CO ₂), blocked vent, thermal expansion	Breach of containment, vapor release	PSV, vacuum breaker, vent scrubber	Human safety	5	2	10	Design vent to handle CO ₂ , check vent lines for fouling			

Figure 8.1: HAZOP for neutralisation reactor

Figure 8.2: Bow-tie diagram for unsuitable CaO piping

Chapter 9. Process operation and control

Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for Start-Up of Acid-Catalysed Biodiesel Production Plant Using Waste Cooking Oil

Document No.: SOP-BD-001

Effective Date: 22 January 2026

Revision: 01

Prepared by: Misa

Approved by: Supervisor

Purpose

To define the standard procedure for safely starting up the production facility based on the acid-catalysed process flowsheet outlined by (Y. Zhang, 2003). It covers all operations involved from feed preparation to product purification for producing biodiesel from waste cooking oil.

This SOP applies to:

Start-Up Procedure

1. System Pre-Checks

- Verify valve positions.
- Ensure vessels are clean and dry.
- Check the instrumentation.
- Confirm reagent levels.

1.2. Feedstock and Reagent Preparation

- Preheat waste oil to 60°C via heat exchanger E-101.
- Prepare methanol (50:1 molar ratio).
- Add sulfuric acid (1.3:1 molar ratio).
- Mix methanol and sulfuric acid in a premix tank.

1.3. Transesterification Reactor Start-Up

- Start R-101 to feed methanol and acid.
- Slowly feed the heated oil and catalyst mixture.
- Maintain conditions of 80°C and 400 kPa.
- Ensure 97% conversion is achieved.

1.4. Methanol Recovery

- Heat T-201, top column at 81°C and bottom column at 116°C.
- Recover 94% of the total for recycling.

1.5. Neutralization

- Cool bottom stream from T-201 to 40–50°C using heat exchanger E-201.
- Add CaO to neutralize acid.
- Monitor pH to ensure complete neutralization.
- Separate CaSO₄ using X-201.

1.6. Water Washing

- Wash the neutralized stream with 1,871 kg/hr of water.
- Separate FAME and glycerol phases.

1.7. FAME Purification

- Distill under vacuum at 40-50 kPa
- Obtain 99.65% purity of FAME.

1.8. Glycerol Purification

- Vacuum distill at 40-50 kPa to purify glycerol to 85–92%.

Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for Abnormal Process Procedures within Biodiesel Production Plant Using Waste Cooking Oil

Document No.: SOP-BD-002

Effective Date: 22 January 2026

Revision: 02

Prepared by: Jack Wyatt

Approved by: Supervisor

Purpose

Provide a standard procedure to manage any abnormal process conditions within the plant utilised to manufacture biodiesel from waste cooking oil. This ensures for certain that any deviation from the normal function and operating parameters is managed within a timely manner, reducing risks to equipment, people and the general environment around them. The SOP also seeks to uphold the production quality of in the processes and process efficiency during abnormal situations.

This SOP applies to:

Abnormal Process Procedure

Standard Operating Procedure for Abnormal Process Conditions Purpose

The objective of this SOP is to provide a standard procedure to manage abnormal process conditions in the plant utilized to manufacture biodiesel. This will make certain that any deviation from the normal operating parameters is managed in a timely manner, reducing risks to the equipment, people, and the general environment around them. The SOP also seeks to uphold product quality and process efficiency during abnormal situations.

Procedure:

2.1 Detection of Abnormal Process Conditions:

- **Monitor Process Parameters:** All important process variables such as temperature, pressure, flow rates, and levels of chemicals should be monitored constantly. Alarms and automatic shutdown mechanisms should warn if they drift past acceptable levels.
- **Indicators of Abnormality:** The abnormal situations might be equipment failure, unexpected change in pressure, temperature or the rate of flows, or unexplained product yield losses. They might be identified by:
 - Visual inspections
 - Process control system alarms
 - Operators feedback
 - Data Analysis
 - Immediate Actions
- **Halt the process (when necessary):** In case the abnormal condition is a safety risk to the equipment or to safety, shutdown the process using the emergency shutdown procedure. Warn all the individuals and evacuate as and when necessary.
- **Isolate Damaged Equipment:** Wherever possible, separate the damaged piece of equipment from the remaining system to protect it from further damage or exposure to safety hazards. This could involve valves closing, pumps shutting down, or de-energisation of electric systems.

2.2 Diagnosis

- **Inspect System and Equipment:** Visually and operationally inspect the system and affected equipment. Check it for leakage and any indication of corrosion, out of pattern vibration, or any defective component/s.
- **Review system logs:** Use the plant control system logs to investigate any abnormal patterns such as deviations in process data, which may be responsible for causing the disturbance.

2.3 Corrective Actions:

- **Reset Process Variables:** If the abnormality is associated with process variables (eg, pressure or temperature), reset them to their best set points that have previously been determined for best operation. Gradually make the changes to avoid placing additional imbalances on the system.
- **Replace or Fix the Equipment:** In case the defective equipment is the source of occurrence of the problem, replace or fix it as early as possible. Maintenance activities can only be undertaken by authorized individuals as per the recommendation of the equipment manufacturer.
- **Rebalance Chemical Additives:** In the event of suspected abnormal chemical reactions that could be caused from wrong methanol or catalyst levels, you would have to implement corrective action in this case being to add the required chemicals or rebalance the batch mixture to desired levels of reaction.

2.4 Return to Normal Operations:

- **Gradual Restarts:** Following corrective action, restart process slowly to a normal operating state. Feedstocks and chemicals are brought back slowly to ensure all control and safety systems are functioning prior to returning to full production.
- **Closely Monitor the Process:** Watch closely the system in the first phase of operation both during and following the removal of the abnormal condition to gain stability. Use real-time data and alarms to determine any potential recurrence of the abnormality

2.5 Documentation and Reporting:

- **Incident Report:** Document the uncommon phenomenon and the identified cause, action is to be taken to rectify the issue and the time it took to do so. Indicate any impact on production and/or quality and any change to procedures in the future.
- **Review and Analysis:** Conduct a root cause analysis after the incidence to ascertain that such incidents do not recur in the future. Involve all the stakeholders in the review to identify any hardware, operational or procedure improvement.
- **Notify Appropriate Authorities:** In case the irregularity resulted in any safety, environmental, or regulatory breach, report to proper authorities immediately as per factory and legal regulations.

2.6 Preventive Measures:

- **Update Operating Procedures:** Use the lessons obtained from the abnormal process condition to revise the standard operating procedures, training guides, or maintenance schedules to reduce the likelihood of recurrence.
- **Training:** All stakeholders are to undergo training to learn how to identify, react to, and avoid uncommon incidents, any issues having been accorded a high priority if they arose during the incident.

CCCU		Canterbury Christ Church University	
Production of Biodiesel Process			
Revision History:		Drawing 1	
1. Final P&ID		Sheet	REV
		2	3

Table 9.1: Control system legend.

Symbol	Denotation
	Level transmitter
	Level controller
	Temperature transmitter
	Temperature controller
	Pressure indicator
	Analyser transmitter
	pH transmitter
	Composition controller
	Level alarm high
	Level alarm low
	Actuated valve
	Manual valve

Chapter 10. Process economic analysis

This chapter contains a coarse economic analysis of the entire acid catalysed transesterification process, using a combination of calculated enthalpy data and heat duty around major process units, as well as literature sources for chemical plants of a similar capacity and mode of production. This analysis focuses on estimating annual expenditure, and contrasting that against annual revenue so as to gain insight into the economic feasibility of the production plant. For this analysis most data gathered was in dollars, and both dollar and pound conversions are given. Values were rounded to the nearest million due to the scale of production. All spot prices were derived from market data and reports primarily from Argus Media, Methanex, IndexBox, S&P Global Commodity Insights, and ESL Fuels Biofuel Market Updates, reflecting market conditions in late 2024 and early 2025, however these prices are subject to market fluctuations.

Capital expenditure

The construction of a 600,000 tonne per year biodiesel production plant naturally results in a large upfront capital investment. Data from between 2020 and 2025 indicates that the total cost for installation may be somewhere between £225 and £300 per annual tonne of capacity. Indeed, other data suggests a 200,000 tonne per year biodiesel plant may cost approximately \$93 million, or around £45 million; thus, there appears to be some consensus in the data as to the rough cost of a biodiesel production plant on a similar scale as the project basis. That said, economies of scale may play a role, therefore it may not necessarily be as simple as multiplying the literature derived cost per tonne capacity by the capacity of our plant, and may not be as simple as scaling the cost of the 200,000 tonne per year plant to match the scale of our 600,000 tonne per year plant. Nonetheless, for the purposes of this project it was deemed a good enough estimate to gain an insight into the rough capita cost such a plant would pose. To account for economies of scale, the lower £225 estimate was taken, resulting in a total capital expenditure of £135 million or if we take the \$93 million for a 200,000 tonne output plant, a total capital cost of \$279 million, or £212 million.

Operational expenditure

The main driving force in the operational expenditure are the feedstocks used. WCO can be obtained at no cost, however this type of WCO remains too low quality to be used without significant pretreatment efforts. Most WCO is minimally pre-treated by collection companies to aid in the sale of WCO as a commercial feedstock, not a waste product. During early 2025, the cost of WCO as a feedstock was approximately \$1200-\$1250 per tonne, equating to roughly between £900 and £950 per tonne. Given the annual WCO requirement of 676,710 tonnes needed to reach the 600,000 target biodiesel output, this means that the annual feedstock expenditure alone totals over £600 million (taking the lower cost due to economies of scale) or using the original unconverted value, \$720 million. This aligns with previous literature findings which stated that a significant majority of production costs of biodiesel are the result of feedstock oil.

Initial methanol expenditure is also significant, however since the methanol is able to be recycled at about a 95% efficiency, the yearly running costs are not nearly as significant, and the first batch of methanol may better be classified as a capital expense. Based on a market price of \$350 to \$400 per tonne, taking the lower value to account for economies of scale, the first year expenditure based on a yearly tonnage requirement of 60980 tonnes results in a cost of \$213 million, or £162 million, and \$11 million, or £8.3 million, each year thereafter.

Sulphuric acid as a reagent is utilised at a much lower tonnage than either WCO or methanol, with 9,850 tonnes per year. Given the current market value of \$160 per tonne, this totals \$1.57 million or £1.2 million.

Calcium oxide is the last reagent considered, with an annual consumption of 56,126 tonnes per year. It exists in solid form, and is therefore easy and cheap to transport. At the current value of \$161 per tonne, the total yearly calcium oxide expenditure totals \$9 million, or £7 million.

Another important consideration when evaluating operational costs is the consumption of water for heat transfer, as well as the energy expenditure of the process units. Based on a continuous heat requirement of 120,240,000 kWh per year found in chapter 5, and taking a spot price of industrial gas of 4.11 pence, the yearly energy cost is approximately £5 million, or \$6.5 million.

Taking these in their totality, the final operational cost is approximately £775 million, or \$950 million, for the first year, and then £622 million, or \$748 million each year thereafter.

Revenue potential and payback period

The 600,000 tonne per year biodiesel plant is projected to make a significant amount of revenue due to the high output, however due to the high capital and operational expenditures, economic viability may be unfeasible. Based on a current biodiesel market value of \$1400 per tonne, the primary revenue stream of biodiesel yields \$840 million per year. The secondary crude glycerol stream valued at a spot price of \$250 per tonne yields a yearly revenue of approximately \$18 million per year. Considering the Renewable Transport Fuel Certificate subsidy of 25 pence per litre, and using the density found in literature in the physiochemical properties table yields a total litre count of 668,896,321 L, this subsidy nets an additional £167 million, or \$220 million. Since biodiesel is eligible for double certificates, these values are also doubled.

Therefore, the primary revenue stream of \$1.3 billion can be compared against the total operational cost of \$748 million and a capital cost of \$481 million (including first year methanol costs) giving a net yearly revenue of \$52 million in the first year of operation, and \$552 million each year thereafter. This means the cost of the plant is paid for within the first year, with a small profit, with a reasonable profit thereafter.

Conclusion

In conclusion, to produce 600,000 tonnes of biodiesel annually using WCO as feedstock, this project found that a plant operating via acid catalysed esterification process aligns most with the sustainability goals while balancing economic viability. A product purity of 99.65% is required to meet EN-14214 standard with a valuable glycerol by product opening another revenue stream for the plant. With a detailed and thorough analysis of the mass balance, the process exhibited high conversion rates.

Compared to other reaction pathways the acid catalysed pathway exhibited superior cost effectiveness as it can treat very low quality WCO, by directly esterifying FFAs. This eliminates a pre-treatment step which complicates the process. However, the amount of methanol required for this treatment route, though implementation of methanol recovery units alleviate this issue, is higher when compared to other pathways. Energy recovery methods such as grand composite curves and heat exchanger networks lower utility costs and reduce the carbon footprint of the plant. Various safety risks arise in the plant from handling hazardous materials such as methanol (flammable), and sulfuric acid (corrosive). Therefore, HAZOP studies, bow tie diagram, and alarm systems integrated to the control loops are outlined in this project. The environmental aspect was also considered throughout the design, a methanol recovery unit improves plant economics and reduces volatile emissions. Economically, the plant will require \$282 million in capital expenditure, the second year operational cost is approximately \$950 million, for the first year, and then or \$748 million each year thereafter. The payback is one year, which is enabled only by the government subsidies of renewable fuel.

The profitability of the plant is challenging to evaluate as WCO as a feedstock means higher running costs, leading to a higher payback period. However, there is no doubt that demand for biodiesel is increasing and will continue to increase as pressures from policy makers force the global fuel supply to include more and more biodiesel. The main factor in making the plant economically viable is UK government subsidies as fossil fuel alternatives offer a more competitive option.

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